

The family Pyramidellidae in the Red Sea. I. The tribe Chrysallidini

La familia Pyramidellidae en el Mar Rojo. I. La tribu Chrysallidini

Anselmo PEÑAS*, Emilio ROLÁN** & Bruno SABELLI***

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ABSTRACT

The present work is the first of a series in which the Pyramidellidae of the Red Sea will be studied. We start with the tribe Chrysallidini, which includes the genera *Helodiamea* (2 species), *Strioturbonilla* (1), *Parthenina* (12), *Pyrgulina* (20), *Chrysallida* (1), *Costabieta* (1), *Miralda* (4), *Oscilla* (10), *Pseudoscilla* (1) and *Babella* (6). In total, there are 58 species, of which 34 are new to science. One species had a preoccupied name and is renamed. Whenever we were able to photograph the type material of the different species, such photos are shown, and the new species are studied, described and represented through micrographs made with the scanning electron microscope.

RESUMEN

El presente trabajo es el primero de la serie en la que se estudiarán los Pyramidellidae del Mar Rojo, empezando en este por la tribu Chrysallidini, en la que se incluyen los géneros *Helodiamea* (2 especies), *Strioturbonilla* (1), *Parthenina* (12), *Pyrgulina* (20), *Chrysallida* (1), *Costabieta* (1), *Miralda* (4), *Oscilla* (10), *Pseudoscilla* (1) y *Babella* (6). En total, son 58 especies de las cuales 34 son nuevas para la ciencia. Una especie tenía un nombre previamente ocupado y recibe un nuevo nombre. Se muestra el material tipo de las especies conocidas que ha podido ser fotografiado y se estudian, describen y representan las nuevas especies mediante microfotografías realizadas con el microscopio electrónico de barrido.

KEY WORDS: Pyramidellidae, Chrysallidini, taxonomy, new species.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Pyramidellidae, Chrysallidini, taxonomía, nuevas especies.

INTRODUCTION

The present work is the first in a series dedicated to the Pyramidellidae of the Red Sea and deals with the tribe Chrysallidini. Given the high number of species found in the study area, we have opted for studying them in separate

parts, and plan to continue with the study of additional tribes in the near future.

For the study and discussion of this tribe, we refer to PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017), who focused on the South and Central

* Olérdola 39, 00880 Vilanova i la Geltrú, Barcelona, Spain.

** Museo de Historia Natural, Universidad de Santiago, Campus Norte, Parque Vista Alegre, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

*** Via Belle Arti 24,40126 Bologna, Italy.

Pacific, detailing the historical background of this tribe starting from CARPENTER'S (1856) description of *Chrysallida* as a subgenus in which he included some species of *Chemnitzia*, until today. In that work, the authors treated a total of 233 species, placed in 19 genera belonging to this tribe, 15 of them previously known and four (*Helodiamea*, *Perheida*, *Ovalina* and *Maricarmenia*) new to science. In the systematic part of the present work, we will keep the conclusions of PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017), who were conservative when it comes to allocate the species to genera.

In addition to the latest work dealing with the Pacific, the authors previously studied this family in the Spanish Mediterranean (PEÑAS, TEMPLADO & MARTÍNEZ, 1996), West Africa (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1998), Atlantic seamounts of the Meteor group (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 1999a) and the Andalusian coast (Iberian Peninsula) (PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2011).

Relatively few Pyramidelloidea species had been described from the Red Sea until now, and for that reason, of the 52 species described in the present work (only for the tribe Chrysalidini), 34, belonging to 10 different genera, are new to science. The first of the works on the molluscs from the Red Sea mentioning Pyramidellids was carried out by SAVIGNY (1817), whose remaining type specimens were illustrated by BOUCHET & DANRIGAL (1982). We highlight the subsequent works of ISSEL (1869), JICKELI (1884) and HORNUNG & MERMOD (1924, 1925), with important presence of Pyramidellidae, and more recently that of EDELMAN-FÜRSTENBERG & FAERSHTEIN (2010).

We must also consider the numerous works of Melvill dedicated to the Pyramidellidae of the Persian Gulf, Gulf of Oman and Arabian Sea, some of whose species have been cited by the above-mentioned authors; MELVILL (1910) summarized and reviewed previous contributions on this family. SELLI (1973) described several fossil species and also BANDEL (2005) described additional fossil species and a few Recent ones

from the Gulf of Aqaba. We have been surprised by the scarcity of recent works describing new species of Pyramidellidae from the Red Sea. Even though not describing new species, BLATTERER (2019) dedicated a large space to this group in his work.

On the other hand, there are several papers dealing with species of Red Sea Pyramidellidae which have penetrated into the Mediterranean, among them the works of AARTSEN & CARROZZA (1979), AARTSEN & GOUD (2006), AARTSEN & HORI (2006), AARTSEN & RECEVIK (1998), BOGI & KHAIRALLAH (1987), LINDEN & EIKENBOOM (1992), MICALI & PALAZZI (1992), OLIVERIO (1993), NOFRONI & TRINGALI (1995), BUZZURRO & GREPPI (1995), BUZZURRO & NOFRONI (1995), GIUNCHI, MICALI, & TISSELLI (2001), MAZZIOTTI, AGAMENNONE & TISSELLI (2002), ÖZTÜRK & AARTSEN (2006), GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

An important part of the material studied comes from the collection of the second author (CER): sediments obtained by immersions in Aqaba (Jordan, 1982) between 5 and 15 meters deep, and in Hurghada (Egypt, 1983) between 10 and 30 meters deep, mainly by José Luis Gonzalez. The rest of the material has been contributed from the Institute of Geology of Bologna and Zoology Museum of Bologna (MZB), from Jordan, Egypt, Sudan, Eritrea and Saudi Arabia. Part of this material was collected by Bruno Sabelli and Marco Taviani, in the Gulf of Aqaba, Abu Ghusum, and other localities.

Only part of the material examined has been used for the study, since a high percentage of shells, difficult to identify because they are eroded or broken, have been rejected.

We have tried to illustrate not only the new species, but also those for which some information is provided. Efforts have been made to present scanning electron micrographs of practically all of the species illustrated.

For the types of protoconch, the terminology of AARTSEN (1987) is used, with the changes adopted by LINDEN & EIKENBOOM (1992), SCHANDER (1994) and PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1997), explained at length in PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2010).

For the scanning electron micrographs (SEM), we have used a Quanta 200 in the Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico a la Investigación (CACTI) of the University of Vigo (operated by Jesús Méndez and Inés Pazos) and also an AVO in the Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico (CACTUS) of the University of Santiago de Compostela (operated by Ramiro Barreiro and Raquel Antón Segurado).

The order in which the species in each genus will be described is that in which they were set out in the preceding key, in an order corresponding to their morphological affinities, which facilitates comparisons and discussions.

In comparison with other species in the study or nearby areas, when these species have not been directly studied by us, we will employ the generic name in which these are currently placed.

Abbreviations:

CAP: Private collection of Anselmo Peñas

CBS: Private collection of Bruno Sabelli

CER: Private collection of Emilio Rolán
CSG Private collection of Sandro Gori,
Livorno, Italy

MCSNG Museo Civico Storia Naturale,
Genova

MHNS Museo de Historia Natural de la
Universidad, Santiago de Compostela

MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire
Naturelle, Paris

MZB Museo di Zoologia, Università di
Bologna

MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias
Naturales, Madrid

NHMUK Natural History Museum of
United Kingdom, London (formerly
BMNH)

Stn Station

s shell

j juvenile shell

= approximately equal

H total height of the shell

h height of the last whorl

D diameter of the last whorl

A height of the aperture

Bathymetric level terms used here:
supralittoral: splash zone, usually not
covered by the water; mesolittoral: the
level between tides; infralittoral: is the
depth between a normal low tide to
about 50 m deep; circalittoral is
between 50 and 200 m; bathyal: more
than 200 m.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Family PYRAMIDELLIDAE Gray, 1840

Tribe CHRYSALLIDINI Saurin, 1958

Genus *Helodiamea* Peñas and Rolán, 2017

Type species: *Elodia elegans* de Folin L. 1873 (= *Odostomia gisna* Dall & Bartsch, 1904, replacement name for *Elodia elegans* de Folin, not *Odostomia (Evalea) elegans* A. Adams, 1860).

Shell small, conical to slightly cyrtocoid, with slightly convex whorls and a deep suture, the last whorl rounded at the periphery. Protoconch heterostrophic, generally of type B, sometimes of type A, with a partly submerged nucleus. Teleoconch whorls with an axial sculpture of generally robust ribs, rounded in profile,

lacking conspicuous spiral sculpture, except sometimes for a cord or peripheral sulcus or some fine striae noticeable on the last whorl.

Aperture pyriform in outline, with a prominent columellar tooth; outer lip simple, not thickened, provided inside with spiral cordlets.

Helodiamea prima n. sp. (Figure 1)

Type material. *Holotype:* Egypt • 1 s (Fig. 1A); Wadi Gimal; 16 m; Stn 90; MZB60234. *Paratypes:* Egypt • 4 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35037. • 15 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MNCN 15.05/200043 (exCER). • 16 s; Zabargad; Stn MR79; MZB60235.

Material examined (67 s): The type material and Egypt • 3 s; Zabargad; Stn 1; MZB. Jordan • 1 s; Aqaba, Yamania; MZB • 5 s; Aqaba, 5–15 m; CAP • 2 s; Aqaba (CSG). Saudi Arabia • 4 s; Jeddah; sample 47 (246); MZB. Eritrea • 2 s; Dahlak; MZB. Sudan • 14 s; Mesharifa; Stn A1; MZB.

Type locality: Wadi Gimal, Egypt, 16 m.

Etymology: The specific name alludes to the circumstance that this is the first species studied in the present work.

Distribution: Common in the littoral and infralittoral areas throughout the Red Sea.

Description: Shell small, solid, conical to sub-oval, milky white, shiny. Protoconch of type C, tending to B, with a diameter of about 250–260 μm and a nucleus of about 100 μm . Teleoconch with four slightly convex whorls, with a moderately high spire, the last whorl rounded at the periphery. Suture shallow, with a narrow subsutural shelf.

Axial sculpture formed by about 22 orthocline ribs, not very high, rounded in profile, wider than their interspaces, disappearing attenuated on the base without reaching the aperture. No spiral sculpture, except for a narrow groove running below the suture.

Aperture sub-oval; columella curved, opisthocline, somewhat reflected outwards, with a robust columellar tooth. In the majority of the specimens there are about six thin spiral internal cordlets. Lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: H= 2.6 mm; D= 1.2 mm; h=1.5 mm; A= 0.95 mm.

Remarks: *Helodiamea attracta* Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water

of the South Pacific, has a smaller and wider shell, with a shorter spire ($h = 70\% H$), the ribs are robust, extended conspicuously on the base and reaching the aperture, and the protoconch is type B in helmet form.

Pyrgulina dautzenbergi Melville, 1910, described from Bombay, has a similar shell but stouter, the whorls are almost flat, stepped, the ribs are more robust, it has a conspicuous spiral cord at the periphery of the last whorl and the protoconch is of type B.

Odostomella? innocens Thiele, 1925, described from Sumatra, Indonesia, has a shell with a megastomiform profile, the last whorl is angled at the periphery, the suture is deeper, has fewer ribs, which are about 16 and well marked, has a spiral cordlet on the periphery of the last whorl and the protoconch is type A with a partly submerged nucleus.

Polemicella piscatorium Saurin, 1959 (figured in ROBBIA ET AL., 2004), described from Viet Nam and recorded in the Holocene of Thailand is similar but its protoconch is type A.

Helodiamea firma n. sp. (Figure 2)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Figs. 2A-B); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35038 (exCER). *Paratypes:* Egypt • 3 s; (Figs. 2C-D); Hurghada; 10–30 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35039 (exCER).

Material examined (4 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin name *firmis*, *a*, *um* which means “firm, solid, stable” alluding to the characteristic of the shell.

Distribution: Collected in the infralittoral of Jordan and Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small but solid, sub-oval, milky white, shiny. Proto-

conch of type C with a diameter of about 290 μm . Teleoconch of three slightly convex whorls, with a moderately high spire ($h = 65\% H$), the last

Figure 1. *Helodiamea prima* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.6 mm, Egypt, Wadi Gimal (MZB); B-D: paratypes, 2.34, 1.75, 1.22 mm, Egypt, Hurgada; 10-30 m (MNHN); E, F: shells, 1.86, 1.68 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5-15 m (CSG); G: protoconch, same as D; H: protoconch from Aqaba.

Figura 1. Helodiamea prima n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,6 mm, Egipto, Wadi Gimal (MZB); B-D: paratipos, 2,34, 1,75, 1,22 mm, Egipto, Hurgada; 10-30 m (MNHN); E, F: conchas, 1,86, 1,68 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5-15 m (CSG); G: protoconcha, misma que D; H: protoconcha de Aqaba.

whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, with a narrow subsutural shelf.

Axial sculpture consisting of about 22 very robust ribs, nearly rectangular in profile, something wider than their interspaces, slightly prosocline, extended conspicuously on the base and

reaching the aperture. There is a very weak cordlet, only visible between ribs, on the periphery of the last whorl, and there are 5 more on the base.

Aperture pyriform; columella curved, opisthocline, with a prominent columellar tooth. Outer lip slightly thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.84 x 0.8 mm; h = 1.21 mm; A = 0.6 mm.

Remarks: We have decided to include this species in the genus *Helodiamea*, since it lacks a spiral sculpture between sutures and instead has the typical cordlets at the periphery and on the base, which can be seen in Figure 2B.

Helodiamea prima n. sp. has a larger shell, but the protoconch is smaller diameter (250-260 μm); the spire is higher, with a more conical profile, the whorls grow more slowly and are more

convex, the last one is more inflated at the periphery; the axial sculpture is more delicate, with the axial ribs not so robust, disappearing attenuated on the base without reaching the aperture; and it has no spiral sculpture on the base.

Pyrgulina dautzenbergi Melville, 1910, has a larger shell, with the protoconch of type B, the teleoconch has a stepped profile of the whorls, has more ribs (about 26), which disappear attenuated at the periphery of the last whorl, and it also lacks a spiral sculpture over the base.

Genus *Strioturbonilla* Sacco, 1892

Strioturbonilla Sacco, 1892. Type species: *Odostomia sigmoidea* Monterosato, 1880.

Subcylindrical shell, with conspicuous axial sculpture on all the whorls, non-conspicuous spiral sculpture, only

spiral microsculpture all over the surface; without columellar tooth. Protoconch type B or C.

Strioturbonilla irregularis n. sp. (Figure 3)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 3A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MZB60250. *Paratypes:* Jordan • 3 s (Figs. 3B-C); same data as for holotype; MZB60251.

Material examined (4 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Gulf of Aqaba, 10 m.

Etymology: The specific name is the Latin word *irregularis*, *is*, alluding to the irregular sculpture of some shells.

Distribution: Only known in the Gulf of Aqaba, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small, not very solid, polymorphic, subcylindrical tending to sub-oval, milky white, shiny. Protoconch of type B, helmet shaped, with a diameter of about 220 μm . Teleoconch with four slightly convex whorls, with a moderately high spire, the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, with a narrow but clear subsutural shelf.

Axial sculpture formed by 16-20 strong, irregular ribs, prolonged on the base to the aperture. Apparently, there is no spiral sculpture, but the teleoconch is covered with spiral micro striae, both on the ribs and in the interspaces, more evident over the base.

Aperture small, sub-oval; columella thin, almost straight, opisthocline,

without visible columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.05 x 0.73 mm; h = 1.1 mm; A = 0.61 mm.

Remarks: The species of this genus are characterized by the absence of macroscopic spiral sculpture, the absence of a columellar tooth and by having a type B protoconch. Our species meets those requirements, and apparently has no spiral sculpture, but it has spiral microsculpture over all the teleoconch.

The new species is clearly different from *Trabecula jeffreysiana* Monterosato, 1884, species of the Mediterranean and West Africa; it also differs from *Trabecula aequilibritas* Peñas & Rolán, 2017, which lives in deep water of Fiji, both of which completely lack a spiral microsculpture.

Figure 2. *Helodiamea firma* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 1.84 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); C: paratype, 1.5 mm, Egypt, Hurghada, 10–30 m (MNHN); D: protoconch of the paratype; E: microsculpture.

Figura 2. *Helodiamea firma* n. sp. A, B: holotipo, 1,84 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); C: paratipo, 1,5 mm, Egipto, Hurgada, 10–30 m (MNHN); D: protoconcha del paratipo; E: microescultura.

Genus *Parthenina* Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883

Parthenina Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1883: 168. Type species by original designation:

Turbo interstinctus J. Adams, 1797, sensu MONTAGU, 1803 [Recent: Devonshire, British Isles].

= *Tiberiella* Coen, 1933: 164. Type species by original designation: *Tiberia pretiosa* Coen, 1933 (= *Turbo interstinctus* Montagu, 1803).

= *Prestoniella* Saurin, 1958: 64. Type species by original designation: *Pyrgulina prestoni* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907 [Recent: Annam, Ben Son beach, Viet Nam].

This genus includes species in which the shell has a definite axial sculpture, and spiral sculpture which comprises, besides the peripheral cord, one or more spiral

threads in the interspaces of the ribs, not covering the entire whorl. The base may be smooth or with spiral sculpture. The protoconch is always of type C.

Figure 3. *Strioturbonilla irregularis* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.05 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 10 m (MZB); B, C: paratypes, 1.8, 1.6 mm, same locality (MZB); D: protoconch; E: microsculpture.

Figura 3. *Strioturbonilla irregularis* n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,05 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 10 m (MZB); B, C: paratipos, 1,8, 1,6 mm, misma localidad (MZB); D: protoconcha; E: microescultura.

Key of the species of the genus *Parthenina*

1. - Base without spiral sculpture 2
 - Base with spiral sculpture 6
2. - Only one spiral cord between sutures 3
 - Two or more cords between sutures 5
3. - Whorls stepped, H/D = 2.2 *scalarum*
 - Whorls not stepped 4
4. - Spire high (h < 50% H), H/D = 2.6, conical elongate *elegantiae* n. sp.
 - Spire short (h = / < 2.2 H), H/D = 2.2, conical wide *tavianii* nom. nov.
5. - Two spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl; whorls convex *cossmanni*
 - 4-5 spiral cords in that interval; whorls *perpetua* n. sp.

- 6. - The ribs are present conspicuously on the base, reaching the aperture 7
- The ribs are faded before reaching the aperture 10
- 7. - Shell conical or truncate-conical, 2 cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl *convoluta* n. sp.
- Shell sub-oval, 3-4 cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl . . . 8
- 8. - The spiral cords occupy half of the interval between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl 9
- The spiral cords occupy two thirds of that interval *sudanensis* n. sp.
- 9. - Whorls convex, 2-3 cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl *nexa* n. sp.
- Whorls flat, 3 cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl . . . *nana*
- 10. - The spiral cords run over the ribs, delimiting rectangular pits, occupying 2/3 of the interval between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl *punctigera*
- The spiral cords are only present in the interspaces of the ribs, occupying as much the half of the interval between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl . . . 11
- 11. - Microsculpture of perforations, three spiral cords on the base . . . *perforata* n. sp.
- Without microsculpture, one spiral cord on the base *unavera* n. sp.

Parthenina cossmanni (Hornung & Mermod, 1924) (Figure 4A-E)

Pyrgulina cossmanni Hornung & Mermod, 1924. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St. Nat. Genova*, 51: 301-302, fig. XVII.
Besla cossmanni - SAURIN, 1959. *An. Fac. Sci. Saigon*, 243, pl. 19, fig. XVII.
Besla cossmanni - ROBBA *ET AL.*, 2004. *La Conchiglia*, 35, supplement to n° 309: 177-178, pl. 25, fig. 2.
Parthenina cossmanni – BLATTERER, 2019: 401, plate 213, fig. 20a, b.

Type material: Not examined.

Material examined (7 s): Jordan • 7 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; CAP (exCER).

Type locality: Eritrea, Massawa, 30 m depth.

Distribution: Known from the infralittoral of Jordan and Eritrea, Red Sea.

Description: In HORNUNG & MERMOD (1924), SAURIN (1959) and ROBBA *ET AL.* (2004). Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 250 µm.

The largest of the figured shells measures 1.5 x 0.65 mm; h = 0.9 mm; A = 0.52 mm.

Remarks: The holotype figured in the original description is larger (2.0 x 0.77 mm) and has almost one whorl more. This species is characterized by its clearly convex whorls, the last one rounded at the periphery, by its numerous ribs (up to 24), flexuous, and by the lack of spiral sculpture on the base.

See comments in *Pyrgulina perpetua* n. sp. and in *Pyrgulina nexa* n. sp. (see below).

Parthenina perpetua n. sp. (Figure 4F-I)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 4F); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35040 (exCER).
Paratypes: Jordan • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100640 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200044 (exCER).

Material examined (6 s): The type material and Egypt • 1 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; CAP (exCER).

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin word *perpetuus, a, um* which means “continuous, without interruption” alluding to the presence of numerous species of this genus in all the works.

Figure 4. A-E. *Parthenina cossmanni* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924). A: shell, 1.5 mm, B-D: shell, 1.09 mm, both from Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); E: protoconch. F-I. *Parthenina perpetua* n. sp. F: holotype, 1.53 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m in MNHN; G, H: paratype, 1.3 mm, Egypt, Hurghada (MNCN); I: protoconch.

Figure 4. A-E. *Parthenina cossmanni* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924). A: concha, 1,5 mm; B-D: concha, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); E: protoconcha. F-I. *Parthenina perpetua* n. sp. F: holotipo, 1,53 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m en MNHN; G, H: paratipo, 1,3 mm, Egipto, Hurgada, en MNCN; I: protoconcha.

Distribution: Known from the infralittoral of Jordan and Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small, not very solid, truncated-conical, milky white.

Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 260 µm. Teleoconch with about three flat whorls, the last one angled at the periphery. Suture deep, canaliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 ribs of almost rectangular profile, ortho-cline, a little arched, which on the upper whorls reach the lower suture but disappear on the last whorl below the peripheral cord and become confused with the growth lines. Spiral sculpture present only in the interspaces of the ribs and occupying only the $\frac{3}{4}$ lowest part of the whorls between sutures; it is formed by four cords, the lower one stronger; on the last whorl there is an additional peripheral cord and a narrower one below the periphery, forming rectangular pits as they intersect the ribs.

Aperture relatively large ($A = 38\%$ H), sub-oval; columella arched, a little reflected towards the exterior determining an evident umbilical chink; columellar tooth pliciform and internal. Outer lip not thickened.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.53 x 0.78 mm; h = 1.05 mm; A = 0.58 mm.

Remarks: *Parthenina cossmanni* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924) is more slender ($H/D = 2.2$ in average against 1.8 in *P. perpetua* n. sp.), it has almost one whorl more with the same dimensions, the whorls are convex, the last one is rounded at the periphery; it has more ribs and these are thinner, the spiral sculpture is formed only by two thin cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, in addition to the peripheral one.

Parthenina plurifuniculata Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of the Marquesas, Vanuatu and Solomon Islands, has a shell of similar profile, although smaller, measuring 1 mm with the same number of whorls. Between sutures, it has the same number of spiral

cords, but these are more robust and of equal thickness, while in *P. plurifuniculata* the lower one is thicker than the rest and, on the base, there is no other cord than the peripheral one.

Babella maestratii n. sp. has a similar profile, but it has almost one whorl more with the same dimensions, the spiral sculpture covers the entire surface of the whorls, and it has eight evident spiral cords on the base, besides the extension of the axial ribs among them.

Pyrgulina lamyi Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, described from the infralittoral of Indochina, has a narrower shell ($H/D = 2.1$), the ribs have a rounded profile, wider than their interspaces, prolonged on the base but attenuated; on the early whorls it has only one spiral cord above the suture, on the base it has two, in addition to the peripheral cord; in the adapical area it has a groove between the ribs and the columellar tooth is prominent.

Pyrgulina prestoni Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907 has a shell with a similar profile, but it has almost one whorl more, with a lesser height (1.3 mm), the suture is deeply canaliculated and the spiral sculpture is different, being formed by numerous very weak spiral cordlets between the axial ribs, covering the entire whorls.

Pyrgulina alicae Hornung & Mermod, 1924 has a shell of similar dimensions, but it is narrower and more conical in profile, has a single spiral cord between sutures and the peripheral cord is thinner; the spiral sculpture is formed by micro-striae all over the teleoconch surface, also on the base.

Parthenina scalarum Peñas & Rolán, 2017 (Figure 5A-D)

Parthenina scalarum Peñas & Rolán, 2017. *Soc. Esp. Malac. ECIMAT*, Vigo: p. 71-72, figs.48, 26A-B.

Type material examined. *Holotype*: Solomon Islands • 1 s; E Guadalcanal; 09°37'S, 160°42'E; 435-461 m; SALOMON 1; stn CP1858; MNHN-IM-2000-32019.

Other material examined: Yemen • 1 s; off Al Hudayda; 14°47'12"N, 42°39'22"E; 76 m depth; on muddy sand; MZB.

Type locality: Solomon Islands, E Guadalcanal, 09°37'S, 160°42'E, 435-461 m.

Figure 5. A-D. *Parthenina scalarum* Peñas & Rolán, 2017. A, B: shell, 2.1 mm (MZB); C: protoconch; D: microsculpture. E, F. *Parthenina elegantiae* n. sp. E: holotype, 2.4 mm, Jordan, Aqaba (MNHN); F: protoconch.

Figura 5. A-D. *Parthenina scalarum* Peñas & Rolán, 2017. A, B: concha, 2,1 mm (MZB); C: protoconcha; D: microescultura. E, F. *Parthenina elegantiae* n. sp. E: holotipo, 2,4 mm, Jordania, Aqaba (MNHN); F: protoconcha.

Distribution: Known from deep water in Solomon Is., Fiji, Vanuatu and Philippines, its distribution is extended to the infralittoral of the Red Sea.

Description: In PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017). Shell small, not very solid, sub-cylindrical tending to truncated-conical, vitreous white. Protoconch of type A, with a diameter a little wider than 300 μm . Teleoconch with 3.5 stepped whorls, with a high spire, and the last two whorls flat concave. Suture deep, undulating, with a subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture 0 about 16 very narrow ribs, slightly swollen adapically, and extended to the base. Spiral sculpture formed by a narrow cordlet placed above the suture, and another one on the periphery of the last whorl.

Aperture sub-oval, with a pliciform columellar tooth a little internal.

Dimensions of the figured shell: 2.1 x 0.95 mm; h = 1.25 mm; A = 0.75 mm.

Remarks: We have not noticed any important differences between the type specimen and that coming from Aqaba, Red Sea, except in the dimensions: the Red Sea shell is slightly larger than the holotype (1.8 x 0.8 mm). It is a species close to the genus *Waikura* Marwick, 1931, hardly comparable with any other Indo-Pacific species.

Pyrgulina comacum Melvill, 1910, described from deep water of the Oman Gulf has a little similarity, but having examined the two syntypes in NHMUK (1912.8.16.38-39) they have clear differences: the profile of the shell is conical, the protoconch is of type A with a nucleus semi-submerged and it has a conspicuous columellar tooth.

Parthenina elegantiae n. sp. (Figure 5E, F)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 5E); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN IM-2000-35041 (exCER).

Material examined (3 s): The type material and Egypt • 1 s; Hurgada; 10–30 m; CAP (exCER) • 1 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Aqaba, Jordan, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is from the Latin word *elegantia*, *ae* which means “distinction, difference, elegance” in reference to the morphology of the shell.

Distribution: Known from the infralittoral of Jordan and Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small, not very solid, conical, regularly elongated vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch relatively small, with a diameter of about 230 μm . Teleoconch with 5–6 flat whorls, with a relatively high spire, the spire whorls angled just above the suture along a spiral cord, the last one rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, almost canaluculate.

Axial sculpture formed by 18 well-marked ribs, nearly rectangular in profile, slightly opisthoclinal, approximately as wide as their interspaces, prolonged on the base where they disappear attenuated without reaching the aperture. Spiral sculpture only in the interspaces, formed by a spiral cord located just above the suture; last whorl with an additional cord at the periphery.

Aperture pyriform, small; columella opisthoclinal, somewhat angled, thin, without visible columellar tooth. Slightly umbilicated. Lip simple.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.4 x 0.9 mm; h = 1.1 mm; A = 0.7 mm.

Remarks: *Parthenina interstincta* (J. Adams, 1797), distributed in the Mediterranean, European and African Atlantic, has a wider shell, the protoconch is larger (about 300 μm), the whorls are flat-convex, the suture is less deep, has more axial ribs, about 22 on the last whorl, which are regularly orthoclinal, wider than their interspaces, not prolonged on the base, the spiral cords of the last whorl are closer together and the aperture is sub-oval with a conspicuous columellar tooth.

Odostomia articulata Hedley, 1909, described from the infralittoral of Australia, has a narrower shell (H/D = 3.2 in front to 2.6 in *P. elegantiae* n. sp.), with

a higher spire ($h = 35\%$ H versus 46% H), the last whorl is angled at the periphery, has fewer ribs which are wider than their interspaces and has a conspicuous columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina redempta Melvill, 1910, described from the infralittoral of Bombay and the Persian Gulf, has a shell profile resembling a *Turbonilla*, with almost stepped whorls, the ribs are orthocline, wider than their interspaces, a slim subsutural belt

prevents that the ribs reach the upper suture; it has spiral grooves on the base and has a conspicuous columellar tooth.

Parthenina convoluta n. sp. has a shell with a more subcylindrical profile, is somewhat wider with a less elevated spire, its protoconch is larger, at least about $260\ \mu\text{m}$, it has more ribs which are wider than their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture and has several evident spiral cordlets on the base.

Parthenina tavianii nomen novum (Figure 6)

Pyrgulina melvilli Hornung & Mermod, 1924. *Ann. Mus. Civ. Stor. Nat. Genova*, 51: 297-298, fig. XII.
Non *Pyrgulina melvilli* Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907. *Journ. Conch.* 54 (3): 185-186, pl. 6, fig. 10.

Type material examined. *Syntype*: Eritrea • 1 s (height: 2.5 mm); Massawa; MCSNG 6067-6130.

Other material examined (6 s, 1 j): Sudan • 1 s; Mesharifa; Stn 1; MZB. Jordan • 4 s, 1 j; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS (exCER). Egypt • 1 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; CAP (exCER).

Type locality: Massawa, Eritrea, Red Sea.

Etymology: The specific name is after Marco Taviani, Director of the Instituto di Geologia Marina in Bologna.

Distribution: Collected in the infralittoral of Jordan, Egypt, and Sudan, in the Red Sea.

Description: Shell small, solid, conical, plump, milk white in colour. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about $270\ \mu\text{m}$. Teleoconch with four flat to flat-convex whorls, with a moderately elevated spire, the last whorl angular at the periphery. Suture deep, canalliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 very robust ribs, rounded in profile, orthocline or prosocline, somewhat wider than their interspaces, extended conspicuously on the base and reaching the aperture. Spiral sculpture only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by a cord located just above the suture, determining a groove below it. Without conspicuous spiral sculpture on the base,

although some shells have some spiral grooves next to the columella.

Aperture sub-oval; columella curved, with a prominent columellar tooth. About six spiral internal cordlets, visible in some shells. Outer lip somewhat thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the shell of figure A: $2.1 \times 1.1\ \text{mm}$; $h = 1.3\ \text{mm}$; $A = 0.7\ \text{mm}$. Dimensions of the largest shell: $2.3 \times 1.1\ \text{mm}$; $h = 1.5\ \text{mm}$; $A = 0.8\ \text{mm}$.

Remarks: We believe that our material basically coincides with that of the original description, and the examined syntype, even when the authors refer to ribs extended to the base as obsolete fillets. They do not show the peripheral cord in the figures, but its presence is mentioned in the description. Our shells are slightly smaller.

Parthenina convoluta n. sp. (Figure 7)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Figs. 07A-B); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35042 (exCER). *Paratypes*: Jordan • 2 s (Figs. 07C-D); same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200045 (exCER).

Material examined (5 s): The type material and Egypt • 2 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin word *convolutus*, a, um participle of the verb *convolvere* which means “to surround” alluding to the spiral cordlets on the base of the last whorl.

Figure 6. *Parthenina tavianii* nom. novum. A: shell, 2.1 mm, Sudan, Mesharifa (MZB); B: shell, 2.3 mm, Aqaba (MHNS); C: shell, 2.1 mm, Mesharifa (MZB); D: protoconch of the shell of figure C; E: protoconch of the shell of figure B.

Figura 6. Parthenina tavianii nom. novum. A: concha, 2,1 mm, Sudán, Mesharifa (MZB); B: concha, 2,3 mm, Aqaba (MHNS); C: concha, 2,1 mm, Mesharifa (MZB); D: protoconcha de la concha de la figura C; E: protoconcha de la concha de la figura B.

Distribution: Known in the infralittoral of Jordan and Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small, not very solid, truncated-conical tending to sub-cylindrical, milk white. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 270 µm. Teleoconch of 4.5 flat-convex whorls, with a rather high spire and the last whorl rounded at the periphery. Suture deep.

Axial sculpture formed by about 20 robust ribs, orthocone or slightly prosocline, nearly rectangular in profile, prolonged on the base to the aperture.

Spiral sculpture only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by one cord on the first two whorls and two on the penultimate, occupying less than the lower half of the whorl; last whorl with one additional peripheral cord and 3 more cords on the base.

Aperture sub-oval; columella curved, opisthocline, without any visible columellar tooth. There is an umbilicus or an umbilical chink. Outer lip not thickened.

Dimensions: the holotype is 2.5 mm in height x 0.98 mm.

Figure 7. *Parthenina convoluta* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 2.5 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); C, D: paratypes, 1.77, 1.5 mm, same locality (MNCN); E: protoconch from the shell of figure D; F: protoconch from other shell.

Figura 7. *Parthenina convoluta* n. sp. A, B: holotipo, 2,5 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); C, D: paratipos, 1,77, 1,5 mm, misma localidad (MNCN); E: protoconcha de la concha de la figura D; F: protoconcha de otra concha.

Remarks: *Egila spiralis* Laseron, 1959, described from the infralittoral of Australia (holotype C.105284 examined) has an acute conical shell, very solid, the whorls are flat, the last one is angled at the periphery, the suture is very deep, canaliculated; it has about 24 ribs rounded in profile, but only one thick spiral supra-sutural cord between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and the columellar tooth is conspicuous.

Parthenina indistincta (Montagu, 1808), from the Mediterranean and the European and North African Atlantic shores, has similar shell profile and dimensions, but the suture is deeper with a narrow sub-sutural shelf, the ribs are opisthocline, not extended conspicuously towards the base to the aperture, the spiral cords, sometimes up to four, above the suture of the last whorl are very close together and the base has no spiral sculpture.

Parthenina sudanensis n. sp. (Figure 8)

Type material. *Holotype*: Sudan • 1 s (Fig. 08A); Mesharifa; Stn A5; MZB60252. *Paratypes*: Sudan • 5 s; same data as for holotype; MZB60236 • 2 s; same data as for holotype MNCN 15.05/200046 • 2 s; same data as for holotype; CAP • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100641.

Material examined (13 s): The type material and *Egypt* • 2 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Sudan, Mesharifa.

Etymology: The specific name refers to the type locality of this species.

Distribution: Known in Egypt and Sudan, Red Sea.

Description: Shell very small, not very solid, conical, milky white, shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 250-260 μm . Teleoconch with 4 convex whorls, a moderately high spire and the last whorl rounded at the periphery. Suture linear and deep.

Axial sculpture formed by a 22-24 rather weak ribs, somewhat irregular, more or less orthocline, approximately as wide as their interspaces, disappearing attenuated at the periphery of the last whorl, whereas on the base the spiral sculpture is more evident. Spiral sculpture only in the interspace of the ribs, formed by one cord above the suture on the first whorl, two or three on the second, three or four on the third and 5 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl occupying only the lower $\frac{3}{4}$ of the whorl; last whorl with an additional peripheral cord and 5-6 more on the base, where the spiral sculpture prevails over the axial ribs.

Aperture sub-oval; columella curved, opisthocline, with a columellar tooth somewhat internal. Outer lip cutting. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: H= 1.83 mm; D=0.8 mm; h = 1.1 mm; A = 0.62 mm.

Remarks: *Trabecula truncatelliformis* Hori & Fukuda, 1999, described from Japan, has a shell of similar dimensions but having, for the same height, one

whorl less, these whorls very convex; it lacks a spiral sculpture on the base and the protoconch is of type B.

Parthenia punctigera A. Adams, 1860, also described from Japan, has a wider shell (H/D = 2), the whorls are angled at their lower third, the last whorl is angled at the periphery and the suture is canaliculate; it has fewer ribs, about 14-16, prolonged on the base to the aperture; it also has 5 spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl but they cover the entire whorl.

Pyrgulina edgarii Melville, 1896, described from Bombay, and cited from Karachi and Viet Nam, has a shell with a ratio H/D = 2.6 against 2.2 in *Pyrgulina sudanensis*, the suture is canaliculate, the ribs are more robust, prolonged on the base to the aperture; the spiral sculpture is formed by faint striae which cover all the teleoconch and the columellar tooth is very prominent and situated outwards.

Parthenina digitiformis Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of Vanuatu and Fiji, has a tiny shell, which has one whorl less, but a more subcylindrical profile, a higher spire, more convex whorls, and the maximum convexity is on the lower third; it has only about 16 ribs, equal to or narrower than their interspaces, the spiral sculpture occupies only the lower half between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl.

Parthenina nexa n. sp. (Figure 9)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Figs. 09A-B); Aqaba; 5-15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35043 (exCER). *Paratypes*: Jordan • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35044 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200047 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100642 (exCER) • 3 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER) • 4 s; Aqaba Gulf; MZB60237 • 2 s; Aqaba, "Marine Station"; MZB60237.

Figure 8. *Parthenina sudanensis* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.83 mm, Sudan, Mesharifa (MZB); B, C: paratypes, 2.25, 2.05 mm, same locality (MZB); D, E: paratypes, 1.73, 1.70 mm, same locality (CAP); F: protoconch.

Figura 8. *Parthenina sudanensis* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,83 mm, Sudán, Mesharifa (MZB); B, C: paratipos, 2,25, 2,05, misma localidad (MZB); D, E: paratipos, 1,73, 1,70 mm, misma localidad (CAP); F: protoconch.

Material examined (18 s): The type material and Egypt • 2 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is from *nexus, a, um* the participle of the verb *necto* which means to join, put together, alluding to the work of the authors bringing aside the descriptions of similar species within each genus.

Distribution: Infralittoral in the Gulf of Aqaba, Jordan and in Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: Shell very small (<2.0 mm), not very solid, sub-oval, vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 260 μm. Teleoconch with three convex whorls, a moderately high spire and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep with a narrow subsutural shelf.

Axial sculpture formed by about 20 robust ribs, rounded in profile, ortho-

cline, approximately as wide as their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture. Spiral sculpture present only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by very thin, inconspicuous cordlets which are 1-2 just above the suture of the first whorl, 2-3 on the second one, 3 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, covering the lower half of this interval; last whorl with an additional peripheral cord and 4-5 more on the base. Under strong

Figure 9. *Parthenina nexa* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 1.7 mm, Jordan, Aqaba (MNHN); D: protoconch of the holotype; E: shell, 1.37 mm, Abu Ghusum (MZB); F: detail of the microsculpture.

Figura 9. *Parthenina nexa* n. sp. A-C: holotipo, 1,7 mm, Jordania, Aqaba (MNHN); D: protoconcha del holotipo; E: concha, 1,37 mm, Abu Ghusum (MZB); F: detalle de la microescultura.

magnification, the surface of the teleoconch appears rough.

Aperture sub-oval; columella slightly curved and opisthocline, with a columellar tooth not prominent but obvious. Without a clear umbilicus but with an umbilical chink after the columella. Outer lip not thickened.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.7 x 0.8 mm; h = 1.1 mm; A = 0.65 mm.

Remarks: *Chysallida palazzii* Micali, 1984, described from the Mediterranean and Eastern Atlantic, has a larger shell, narrower (H/D = 2.5 compared to 2.1 in *Parthenina nexa* n. sp.), the axial ribs are rather flexuose, it has more spiral cords, closer together and thicker and it does not have a columellar tooth.

Parthenina cossmanni (Hornung & Mermod, 1924), described from the Red

Sea and cited from Viet Nam and Thailand, has a slightly larger shell (2 mm) but with one more whorl and narrower (H/D = 2.6); the spire is higher (h = 50% H compared with 65% in *Parthenina nexa* n. sp.); the last whorl is rounded at the periphery, has more axial ribs, in the previous whorls have only one spiral cordlet above the suture and three between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl.

Pyrgulina perforata n. sp. is smaller, with a more conical profile and the protoconch is also smaller (210 μ m), the whorls are less convex, the suture is deeper, canaliculate, has fewer ribs (14), which are half the width of their interspaces, and do not reach the aperture conspicuously; the spiral sculpture is more evident, with thicker spiral cords and only 3 on the base, in addition to the

peripheral one. It has a microsculpture on its surface, formed by minute pits, and the columellar tooth is more internal.

Parthenina nana (Hornung & Mermod, 1924) has a similar shell but is smaller and narrower (H/D x 2.3 vs.

2.1), also has a smaller protoconch; the whorls are less convex, it has fewer ribs, slightly narrower than their interspaces; on the second whorl it has only one spiral cord while *P. nexa* has 2 or 3, and the aperture is smaller and narrower.

Parthenina nana (Hornung & Mermod, 1924) (Figure 10A, B)

Pyrgulina nana Hornung & Mermod, 1924. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St. Nat. Genova*, 51: 300-301, fig. 15. Not *Chrysallida nana* A. Adams, 1861.

= *Chrysallida micronana* ÖZTÜRK & VAN AARTSEN, 2006. *Aquatic Invasions*, 1 (4): 241-244.

= *Pyrgulina nana* – GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL., 2014. *Atl. Conch. Mar. Med.*, vol. 5: figs. 218-219.

Type material examined. *Syntypes*: Eritrea • 3 s; Massawa; 10–30 m depth; MCSNG 6501-6531, 6587-6620, 6693-6720, 6796-6833.

Material examined (5 s): The type material and Jordan • 2 s; Aqaba, Yamania; 2 m; MZB.

Type locality: Massawa, Eritrea, 10-30 m depth.

Distribution: Species described from the Red Sea and recorded in the Eastern Mediterranean (Turkey, Lebanon and Israel).

Description: In HORNUNG & MERMOD (1924), ÖZTÜRK & VAN AARTSEN (2006) as *Chrysallida micronana*, and in GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014). Shell minute, sub-oval to truncate-conical, milky white. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 240 µm. Teleoconch with three flat-convex whorls, a moderately high spire and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture not very deep with a narrow subsutural shelf.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 ribs of rectangular profile, orthocline, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture. Spiral sculpture present only in the interspaces of ribs, formed by one cord located just above the suture on the first two whorls, three between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl occupying only 50% of this interval, last

whorl with an additional peripheral cord, and 5 more on the base.

Aperture sub-oval; columella curved, opisthocline, with a weak columellar tooth, somewhat internal. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

The largest of the syntypes examined measures 1.58 mm. Dimensions of the figured shell: 1.6 x 0.65 mm; h = 0.9 mm; A = 0.46 mm.

Remarks: In our opinion, this species must be placed in the genus *Parthenina* and not in *Pyrgulina*, because the spiral sculpture does not cover the entire teleoconch.

Pyrgulina perforata n. sp. has a shell with similar profile and size, but it is rather cyrtocoid tending to subcylindrical form, the whorls are more convex, the last one rounded at the periphery, the suture is deeper, canaliculate, it has fewer ribs (about 14) being more robust, the ribs do not reach the aperture and on the base there are only 3 spiral cords.

See comments in *P. nexa*.

Parthenina cf. *punctigera* (A. Adams, 1860) (Figure 10C-F)

Parthenia punctigera A. Adams, 1860. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 3 (6): 415. A. Adams, 1863. *Jour. Proc. Linn. Soc. London*, 7: 4.

Chrysallida punctigera (A. Adams, 1860) - Tsuchida & Hori, 1996. *Bull. Nat. Sci. Mus. Tokyo*, 22 (4): 237-238, pl.4, fig. 7.

Linopyrga punctigera (A. Adams, 1860) - Okutani, 2000. *Mar. Moll. Japan*, fig. 140.

Trabecula punctigera (A. Adams, 1860) - Higo et al., 2001. *Cat. Bib. Mar. Moll. Japan*, fig. G4392.

Figure 10. A, B. *Parthenina nana* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924). A: shell, 1.6 mm, Jordan, Yamanía, Aqaba, 3 m (MZB); B: protoconch. C-F. *Parthenina cf. punctigera* (A. Adams, 1860). C-E: shells, 1.35, 1.46, 1.40 mm, Sudan, Mesharifa (MZB); F: sculpture.

Figura 10. A, B. *Parthenina nana* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924). A: concha, 1,6 mm, Jordania, Yamanía, Aqaba, 3 m (MZB); B: protoconcha. C-F *Parthenina cf. punctigera* (A. Adams, 1860). C-E: conchas, 1,35, 1,46, 1,40 mm, Sudán, Mesharifa (MZB); F: escultura.

Type material: Probably type material (NHMUK 1996495). Examined.

Material examined (3 s): Sudan • 3 s; Mesharifa; MZB.

Type locality: Sado, Japan, 30 fathoms.

Distribution: Known in the infralittoral and circalittoral from various locations in Japan, it has a wide distribution to the infralittoral of the Red Sea.

Description: In A. ADAMS (1860). Shell minute, solid, conical to sub-oval, milky white. Protoconch of the type A. Teleoconch of nearly four flat-convex

whorls, with a moderately high spire. Suture deep, canaliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 orthocline ribs, not very thick but elevated, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, prolonged attenuated on the base, where they are confused with the growth lines. Spiral sculpture formed by cords almost

as wide as the ribs, overriding them forming rectangular pits; there is one cord on the first and another on the second whorl, two in the third and four between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl; last whorl with an additional peripheral cord and 5 more on the base, prevalent over the axial sculpture.

Aperture sub-oval; columella slightly curved, opisthocline, with an oblique columellar tooth, quite internal. Not umbilicated.

The shell (probably a syntype) examined from NHMUK measures 1.6 mm. The largest shell from our material from the Red Sea measures: 1.46 x 0.75 mm; h = 0.95 mm; A = 0.54 mm.

Parthenina perforata n. sp. (Figure 11)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Figs. 11A-D); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35045 (ex CER). *Paratypes*: Jordan • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35046 (ex CER) • 3 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200049 (ex CER) • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100643 (ex CER) • 6 s; same data as for holotype; MZB60253 (ex CER) • 3 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (ex CER).

Material examined (16 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name refers to the micro-perforations seen on SEM micrographs.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Aqaba, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute (<1.7 mm) but solid, cyrtocoenoid to subcylindrical, vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 210 µm. Teleoconch with three flat-convex whorls, the last one rounded at the periphery, and a moderately high spire. Suture deep, canaliculate, with a sub-sutural shelf.

Axial sculpture formed by about 14 robust ribs, slightly prosocline, of nearly rectangular profile, wider than their interspaces, prolonged attenuated on the base, not definitely reaching the aperture. Spiral sculpture only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by conspicuous cords, one above the suture of the first whorl, 1-2 on the second and 3 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, occupying only the lower half of that interval; last

Remarks: The shell from the Red Sea has a more oval profile, while those from Japan are more tapered and with slightly more convex whorls, but we do not notice any differences in the spiral and axial sculpture.

Regarding this widely separated population, we think that this may be a convergence of characters, since it seems unlikely that a species of mollusc from Japan could also be living in the Red Sea waters.

When available material with soft parts can be studied from both countries, their DNA must be checked to ascertain if they are two different species.

whorl with an additional peripheral cord and 3 more on the base. Under strong magnification, a microsculpture formed by very small punctures can be seen on the entire surface of the teleoconch, more evident in the interspaces of the ribs.

Aperture relatively small, sub-oval; columella slightly curved, opisthocline, with a clear columellar tooth, but somewhat internal. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.5 x 0.64 mm; h = 0.93 mm; A = 0.5 mm.

Remarks: See comments in *Parthenina nana*, *Pyrgulina nexa* n. sp. and in *Pyrgulina sudanensis* n. sp.

Besla gabriellae Saurin, 1959, described from the infralittoral of Viet Nam and cited in PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017) from the circalittoral of Solomon Islands, has a shell of similar height, but it is narrower, the protoconch is larger (290 µm), the spire is higher, with

Figure 11. *Parthenina perforata* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 1.5 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); C: protoconch of the holotype; D, E: microsculpture and detail of the holotype.

Figura 11. *Parthenina perforata* n. sp. A, B: holotipo, 1,5 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); C: protoconcha del holotipo; D, E: microescultura y detalle del holotipo.

almost one whorl more at the same height, the whorls are flat, strongly angled above the suture in the upper whorls, and the spiral sculpture is less conspicuous.

Pyrgulina edana Melvill, 1910, described from Bombay, has a slightly larger shell. The examined figured syntype (NHMUK 1912.8.16.49) is wider, measuring 1.75 x 0.85 mm, with a ratio H/D = 2, the suture is more deeply canaliculate, it has more axial ribs

(about 22), clearly prosocline, has two spiral cords between sutures and the columellar tooth is prominent.

Pyrgulina unavera n. sp. has a shell of similar size, but its profile is rather truncate-conical, the suture is not so deep; it has more ribs, about 20, not as wide as their interspaces, not prolonged on the base to the aperture, the spiral sculpture is more delicate with finer and more separated cordlets, and on the base there is only one spiral cord.

Parthenina unavera n. sp. (Figure 12A-C)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 12A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35047 (exCER). *Paratypes*: Jordan • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200048 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (4 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is the fusion of the Latin words *unus*, *a*, *um* which means “one” and the adverb *vero* which means “really” alluding to the fact that this is definitely a new species in this genus.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Aqaba, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute, not very solid, truncate-conical tending to sub-cylindrical, vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 250 µm. Teleoconch of 3 ½ flat-convex whorls, the last one rounded at the periphery, and a moderately high spire. Suture deep, with a narrow subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture formed by about 20 robust ribs, of rounded profile, orthocline, approximately as wide as their interspaces, prolonged attenuated on the base, without reaching conspicuously the aperture. Spiral sculpture present only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by one cordlet above the suture of the first whorl, two on the second and three between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, very sep-

arated from each other; last whorl with an additional peripheral cordlet and another one very weak on the base.

Aperture sub-oval; columella curved, opisthocline, with a clear columellar tooth. Without a clear umbilicus but with a narrow umbilical chink. Outer lip not thickened.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.58 x 0.7 mm; h = 0.97 mm; A = .55 mm.

Remarks: See comments in *Pyrgulina perforata* n. sp.

Chrysallida intermissa Thiele, 1925 has a shell of similar size and profile, but the whorls are flat, the last one strongly angled at the periphery, it has fewer ribs, about 15, and only has one spiral cord between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, in addition to the peripheral one.

Genus *Pyrgulina* A. Adams, 1863

Pyrgulina A. Adams, 1863. *Proc. Linn. Soc. London*, 7: 4. Type species: *Chrysallida casta* A. Adams, 1861, subsequent designation by DALL & BARTSCH, 1904, p. 11 [Kala-Hai and Shan-Tung, China].

= *Eupyrgulina* Melvill, 1910. *Proc. Malac. Soc. London*, 9: 199-200, pl. 6, fig. 5. Type species: *Pyrgulina dautzenbergi* Melvill, 1910, subsequent designation by SCHANDER, VAN AARTSEN & CORGAN, 1999 [Bombay, India].

= *Contraxiala* Laseron, 1956. *Austr. Jour. Mar. & Freshwat. Res.*, 7 (3): 85, fig. 88. Type species: *Contraxiala obliqua* Laseron 1956; original designation [Queensland, Australia].

Here we include species with a conspicuous axial sculpture and a spiral sculpture which occupies the entire height of the whorls including the base of the last whorl; this genus-level diagnostic character will not be repeated in

the species accounts. The spiral sculpture may be formed by grooves, threads or cordlets, and may be present only in the interspaces between the ribs, or override them. The protoconch is type C.

Key of the species of the genus *Pyrgulina*

- 1. - Whorls stepped 2
- Whorls not stepped 8

Figure 12. A-C. *Parthenina unavera* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.58 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratype, 1.52 mm, same locality (MNCN); C: protoconch. D-G. *Pyrgulina carmeloi* n. sp. D, E: holotype, 2.75 mm, Jordan, Aqaba (MNHN); F, G: detail of the microsculpture.

Figura 12. A-C. Parthenina unavera n. sp. A: *holotipo*, 1,58 mm, *Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m* (MNHN); B: *paratipo*, 1,52 mm, *misma localidad* (MNCN); C: *protoconcha*. D-G. *Pyrgulina carmeloi* n. sp. D, E: *holotipo*, 2,75 mm, *Jordania, Aqaba* (MNHN); F, G: *detalle de la microescultura*.

- 2. - Without columellar tooth 3
- With columellar tooth 5
- 3. - Spiral sculpture formed by grooves, shell wide ($H/D < 2$) *carmeloi* n. sp.
- Spiral sculpture formed by cords 4
- 4. - The cords override the ribs, outer lip thick *isae* n. sp.
- The cords are only in the interspaces of the ribs, outer lip cutting . . . *permansa* n. sp.
- 5. - Spiral sculpture formed by grooves or striae *pirinthella*
- Spiral sculpture formed by cords 6
- 6. - The ribs are prolonged on the base to the aperture, 9-10 spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl *quinqueflexa* n. sp.
- The ribs are faded on the base and do not reach the aperture 7
- 7. - Shell small, with subsutural step *permanens* n. sp.
- Shell minute, with subsutural shoulder *lineotuber* n. sp.
- 8. - Without peripheral cord 9
- With peripheral cord 19
- 9. - The ribs are prolonged on the base to the aperture 10
- The ribs are faded on the base and do not reach the aperture 12
- 10. - Shell subcylindrical, small, spire elevated, 14-15 spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl *microtuber* n. sp.
- Shell sub-oval, minute, spire short, 8-9 spiral cords 11
- 11. - Shell scarcely robust, outer lip not thickened, spiral cords not strong . . . *scabra* n. sp.
- Shell very robust, outer lip thickened, spiral cords strong . . . *minusgranum* n. sp.
- 12. - Shell subcylindrical, whorls flat-convex *condita* n. sp.
- Shell sub-oval or truncate-conical 13
- 13. - The axial ribs do not reach the aperture, shell minute, conical, ribs prosocline cf. *pretiosa*
- The ribs are prolonged more or less conspicuously on the base, down to the aperture 14
- 14. - Spire short ($h = 65\% H$), sub-oval *lacrima* n. sp.
- Spire elevated ($h = / < 60\% H$), conical or cyrtocooid 15
- 15. - Shell regularly conical, the last whorl angled at the periphery *erecta* n. sp.
- Shell cyrtocooid, last whorl rounded or broadly rounded at the periphery . . 16
- 16. - Shell pupoid, peristome continuous *collecticia*
- Shell cyrtocooid, peristome not continuous 17
- 17. - Spire elevated, 15 spiral cords on the base, columellar tooth very prominent *linomicalii* n. sp.
- Spire not very elevated, 10-12 spiral cords on the base, columellar tooth hardly prominent 18
- 18. - Ribs prosocline, $H/D = 2.7$, spiral cords narrower than their interspaces *prosoribs* n. sp.
- Ribs orthocline, $H/D = 2.5$, spiral cords wider than their interspaces . . . *maiae*
- 19. - Base with wide spiral cords, shell truncate-conical *craticulata*
- Base without conspicuous spiral sculpture, shell definitely conical *alicae*

Pyrgulina carmeloi n. sp. (Figure 12D-G)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 12D-E); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35048 (exCER).

Paratypes: Jordan • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200051 (exCER).

Material examined (2 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Carmelo López del Brío, of Madrid, friend of the first author.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small (<3 mm), not very solid, broadly conical, scalariform, whitish, slightly shiny. Protoconch of type C, with a diameter of about 320 μ m. Teleoconch with a little over three whorls, almost flat, very stepped, the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Spire moderately high (h = 70% H). Suture shallow, undulating, with a wide angled shoulder below it.

Axial sculpture formed by about 16 orthocone ribs, angled, elevated, much narrower than their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture. Spiral sculpture present only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by numerous grooves, narrow, equidistant, only 7-8 between the sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and about 15 more on the base, becoming tighter where reaching the aperture. In addition there are numerous spiral striae on the shoulder.

Aperture sub-oval; columella curved, opisthocline; no columellar tooth. Outer lip narrow. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.75 x 1.4 mm; h = 1.85 mm.

Remarks: *Pyrgulina spifunifortis* Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of the Solomon Islands, has a shell of similar dimensions, also with stepped whorls and with a carinate shelf at the uppermost part of the whorls, but

there is a more distinct cord on the shoulder and a depression below it; the axial ribs form projections on the shoulder and there are much more (about 16) spiral grooves between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, the upper ones nearly obsolete.

Mumiola carbacea Melvill, 1904, described from deep water of the Persian Gulf (holotype NHMUK 1905.6.12.14 examined), has a shell somewhat higher, narrower (H/D = 2.3 against 1.9 in *P. carmeloi* n. sp.), the ribs are lower, and they are slightly opisthocline although in the original description are mentioned as orthocone; the spiral sculpture is formed by very thin cordlets, about six between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and 8 more, very weak; on the base; it has a weak columellar tooth, although somewhat internal.

Pyrgulina partimcostae Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of the Solomon Islands and Madagascar, also has a shell of similar profile but smaller and also the protoconch is smaller; it has a subsutural shelf with a depression below it, the ribs are poorly marked and disappear attenuated below the periphery of the last whorl; the spiral sculpture consists in about 7 spiral grooves, not equally spaced, between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl but there are only eight of them on the base, more evident.

Pyrgulina isae n. sp. (Figure 13)

Type material. *Holotype*: Egypt • 1 s (Figs. 13A-B); Hurghada; 10–30 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35049 (exCER).

Material examined (3 s): The type material and Jordan • 1 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; CAP • 1 s; Aqaba “Marine Station”; 18 m; MZB.

Type locality: Egypt, Hurghada, 10-30 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Isabel “Isa” Segura Muñoz, Forestry Engineer, of Madrid, good friend of the first author.

Distribution: Infralittoral of Egypt and Jordan, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small (<2.5 mm), rather solid, conical to subcylindrical, whitish, slightly shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 260 μm . Teleoconch with 3.5 flat-convex whorls, stepped, the last one broadly rounded at the periphery. Spire moderately elevated. Suture shallow with a wide sub-sutural shelf.

Axial sculpture in the teleoconch, formed by about 16 robust ribs, rounded in profile, arched, narrower than their interspaces, extended conspicuously on the base down to the aperture, also reaching the upper suture and becoming narrower on the subsutural shelf. Spiral sculpture present on the entire teleoconch, except on the subsutural shelf, where there is a grainy microsculpture; it is formed by faintly marked cordlets, overriding the ribs, more visible on the base and next to the outer lip; there are 12 cordlets on the penultimate whorl, 13-14 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl and about 15 more on the base.

Aperture small, narrow, semi-circular; columella almost straight, thickened, opisthocline, without a visible columellar tooth. Outer lip thickened by the 1st rib, with the spiral cords continued to its innermost edge. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.3 x 1.05 mm, h = 1.45 mm; A = 0.9 mm.

Remarks: This species differs clearly from *Pyrgulina pirinthella* Melville, 1910. The authors studied and photographed the holotype of the latter in the NHMUK (1912.8.16.47), the same illustrated in BUZZURRO & NOFRONI (1995). It is a nearly cylindrical species with a delicate sculpture, both axial and spiral, whose spiral cords are not continued on the ribs and in which the aperture is oval.

Pyrgulina? problematica Hornung & Mermod, 1924 is smaller (1.75 x 0.71 mm) with the same number of whorls, has only 9 ribs, thin and sharp in their upper part, the spiral sculpture is formed by numerous cordlets and is present only in the interspaces of the ribs; it has a well marked columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina tenerrima (Melville, 1906). The figured syntype (NHMUK 1906.10.23.38) has been examined and it has a subcylindrical shell with a higher spire, has less axial ribs, which are faded on the base below the periphery without reaching the aperture, spiral sculpture is slighter, present only in the interspaces, not overriding the ribs; there is a columellar tooth although internal, and spiral cordlets can be observed inside the aperture.

Pyrgulina permansa n. sp. (Figure 14)

Type material. *Holotype:* Egypt • 1 s (Fig. 14A); Hurghada; 10–30 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35050. *Paratypes:* Egypt • 2 s (1 of them juvenile); same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200052 (ex CER).

Material examined (4 s): The type material and Jordan • 1 s; Aqaba, "Marine Station"; 18 m; MZB; **Type locality:** Egypt, Hurghada, 10–30 m.

Etymology: The specific name is the participle of the Latin verb *permaneo*, which means "to remain", assuming that this species is bound to remain in the future in the genus in which it is now placed.

Distribution: Infralittoral of Egypt and Jordan, Red Sea.

Description: Shell very small (<2 mm), very fragile, conical tending to sub-oval, whitish, a little shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 250 μm . Teleoconch with more than three stepped whorls, convex, the last one rounded at the periphery, and a

moderately high spire (h = 60% H). Suture deep, with an apparent subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 flexuous ribs, nearly orthocline, rounded in profile, nearly two times narrower than their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture. Spiral sculpture present only in the

Figure 13. *Pyrgulina isae* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 2.3 mm, Hurghada, 10-30 m (MNHN); C: protoconch; D-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 13. *Pyrgulina isae* n. sp. A, B: holotipo, 2,3 mm, Hurgada, 10-30 m (MNHN); C: protoconcha; D-F: microescultura y detalle.

interspaces of the ribs, formed by almost equidistant cordlets, somewhat narrower than their interspaces; there are 8-9 cordlets on the penultimate whorl,

continued on the last whorl, and 8 more on the base. Under strong magnification, the surface can be seen covered by irregular spiral microstriae.

Figure 14. *Pyrgulina permansa* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.7 mm, Egypt, Hurgada, 10-30 m (MNHN); B: paratype, 1.62 mm, same locality, 18 m (MNCN); C-E: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 14. *Pyrgulina permansa* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,7 mm, Egipto, Hurgada, 10-30 m (MNHN); B: paratipo, 1,62 mm, misma localidad, 18 m (MNCN); C-E: microescultura y detalle.

Aperture sub-oval, relatively large; columella curved, opisthocline, without a visible columellar tooth. Umbilicus narrow. Outer lip thin, sharp.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.7 x 0.8 mm; h = 1.05 mm; A = 0.65 mm.

Remarks: *Mumiola carbacea* Melvill, 1904 has a much larger shell (3 x 1.3 mm), and is more robust, the ribs are angled in profile, opisthocline, about 4 times narrower than their interspaces, the spiral sculpture consists in six very

thin cordlets between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, besides one thicker at the edge of the shoulder; it has a columellar tooth although internal.

Pyrgulina pluricircumversa Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of the Philippines, also has a somewhat larger shell, the protoconch is larger (300 μm), the teleoconch whorls are less stepped, the suture is very deep, with a narrow subsutural shelf; it has about 24

prosocline, almost laminar axial ribs on the last whorl.

Turbonilla perscalata Hedley, 1909, described from the infralittoral of Australia, has a larger and narrower shell, the last whorl is broadly rounded at the periphery, the ribs are as wide as their interspaces, the spiral sculpture is less conspicuous, the aperture is very small, sub-quadrangular, with a visible columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina pirinthella Melvill, 1910 (Figure 15)

Pyrgulina pirinthella Melvill, 1910. *Proc. Mal. Soc. London*, 9 (3): 201-202, pl. 6 fig. 9.

Pyrgulina pirinthella - HORNUNG & MERMOD, 1924. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St. Nat. Gen.*, 300.

Pyrgulina pirinthella - BUZZURRO & NOFRONI, 1995. *Notiz. CISMA*, 41-43, fig. 1.

Type material examined. *Holotype*: Pakistan • 1 s (figured in BUZZURRO & NOFRONI, 1995); off Karachi Harbour; NHMUK 1912.8.16.47.

Other material examined (2 s): Egypt • 2 s; Hurghada; 15 m; MZB.

Type locality: Off Karachi Harbour.

Distribution: Karachi, Pakistan. HORNUNG & MERMOD (1924) recorded it from Massaua, Eritrea. We increase its distribution to the infralittoral of the Hurghada, Red Sea.

Description: In MELVILL (1910) and in BUZZURRO & NOFRONI (1995). Shell very small, subcylindrical, not very solid. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 280 μm . Teleoconch with about 3.5 stepped whorls, the last one broadly rounded at the periphery, and a high spire ($h = 55\% H$), Suture not very deep, with a subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18-20 ribs, rounded in profile, approximately as wide as their interspaces, prolonged attenuated on the base. These ribs are orthocone or slightly prosocone on the last whorl. Spiral sculpture consisting in numerous and very narrow furrows, overriding the ribs. Under great magnification, the surface appears to be rough.

Aperture small, sub-oval; columella narrow, arched, with a columellar tooth a little internal. Outer lip thin, almost cutting. Shell not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the largest shell figured: 1.63 x 0.6 mm; $h = 0.9$ mm; $A = 0.5$ mm.

Remarks: The majority of the previous descriptions or comments related to this species have been tentative and, in our opinion, were wrong except for those of BUZZURRO & NOFRONI (1995) who examined the type material. Probably, the shell described by MELVILL (1910) was not fresh, as was our impression when we examined the holotype; however we believe that our material belongs to this species.

In AARTSEN *ET AL.* (1989: fig. 5) and in ZENETOS *ET AL.* (2004) a shell similar to *Pyrgulina pirinthella* is illustrated, and also GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI *ET AL.* (2014: fig. 220) figured a shell as *Pyrgulina* cf. *pirinthella*. In our opinion, all those are very different from the type material examined of this species, and we believe that these shells from the Eastern Mediterranean are more coincident with our *P. microtuber* n. sp. (see below)

Pyrgulina permanens n. sp. has a rather larger shell with the same number of whorls, is narrower ($H/D = 2.6$ in front to 2.3 in the holotype of *P. pirinthella*) with a higher spire, has a less stepped profile, with a subsutural shelf while *P. pirinthella* has a shoulder, has fewer ribs but more robust, and the columellar tooth, although quite internal, is conspicuous

Figure 15. *Pyrgulina pirinthella* Melvill, 1910. A, B: shells, 1.52 and 1.63 mm, Hurghada, Egypt, 15 m (MZB); C-D: shell of fig. B in apical view, and detail of the protoconch; E: protoconch of other shell; F-I: sculpture and details.

Figura 15. Pyrgulina pirinthella Melvill, 1910. A, B: conchas, 1,52 and 1,63 mm, Hurgada, Egipto, 15 m (MZB); C: concha de la fig. B en vista apical, y detalle de la protoconcha; E: protoconcha de otro ejemplar; F-I: escultura y detalle.

Figure 16. *Pyrgulina quinqueflexa* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.8 mm, Jordan, Aqaba (MNHN); B: protoconch; C-E: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 16. *Pyrgulina quinqueflexa* n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,8 mm, Jordania, Aqaba (MNHN); B: protoconcha; C-E: microescultura y detalle.

Pyrgulina quinqueflexa n. sp. (Figure 16)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 16A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35051 (exCER).

Paratypes: Jordan • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200053 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100644 (exCER) • 1 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (ex CER).

Material examined (6 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name alludes to the 5 whorls of the teleoconch, from the Latin *quinque* “five” and *flexus, a, um* “inflection point”.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small (<3 mm), solid, subcylindrical, vitreous white, somewhat shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diam-

eter of about 260 µm. Teleoconch with five convex whorls, the last one rounded at the periphery. Spire relatively high ($h < 45\% H$). Suture rather deep with an evident subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture formed by about 14 elevated ribs, as wide as their interspaces, rounded in profile, rather orthocone, prolonged on the base to the umbilical area, although attenuated. Spiral sculpture formed by equidistant cordlets, as wide as their interspaces, overrunning the ribs, more clearly so on the last whorl; there are about 9-10 cordlets between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl and 10 more on the base. In addition, under strong magnification the entire surface shows a microsculpture of granules along spiral lines.

Aperture small, sub-oval; columella curved, opisthoclinal, with a clear columellar tooth. Without any clear umbilicus but with an umbilical chink, into which the axial ribs penetrate. Outer lip not thickened.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.8 x 0.9 mm; h = 1.2 mm; A = 0.68 mm.

Remarks: See comments in *Pyrgulina adducta* and in *Pyrgulina lineotuber* n. sp.

Pyrgulina tenerrima (Melville, 1906) (synonym: *Pyrgulina nigraerupis* Saurin, 1959, two syntypes examined in MNHN; see also ROBBA ET AL., 1993), has a smaller shell, wider (H/D = 2.6), with a less high spire (h > 50% H); the whorls are more obviously stepped due to the angular shoulder, the ribs are less robust, at least twice as narrow as their interspaces, and they disappear at the periphery of the last whorl; the spiral sculpture is more delicate in the interspaces of the ribs, the columellar tooth is more conspicuous and the aperture is narrower and has inner spiral cordlets.

Pyrgulina rudicostae Peñas & Rolán 2017, described from deep waters of New Caledonia, Vanuatu, Fiji, Solomon Islands and Madagascar, has a shell of similar size but wider (H/D = 2.5), the ribs are prosoclinal, the spiral sculpture is more conspicuous and formed by 6 spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl; it lacks a columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina permanens n. sp. (Figure 17)

Type material. Holotype: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 17A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35052 (exCER). Paratypes: Jordan • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35053 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200054 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100645 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (9 s, 1 j): The type material and Egypt • 1 s, 1 j; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MZB.

Type locality: Aqaba, Jordan, 5–15 m (exCER)

Etymology: The specific name is from the Latin word *permanens, tis* which means “lasting” alluding to the expected permanence of this species in the same genus as those studied in this group.

Distribution: Infralittoral of Egypt and Jordan, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small (<2.5 mm), solid, subcylindrical, narrow (H/D = 2.6), milky white, somewhat shiny. Protoconch of type C, with a diameter of about 290 µm. Teleoconch with four stepped whorls, the last one broadly rounded at the periphery, and with a high spire (h = 44% H). Suture shallow with a subsutural shelf, nearly carinate at the edge.

Axial sculpture formed by about 14 ribs of angular profile, orthocone or prosoclinal, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, disappearing attenuated at the periphery of the last whorl

without reaching the aperture. Spiral sculpture present only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by conspicuous cordlets, which are about 12 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, approximately as wide as their interspaces; last whorl with about 15 additional striae on the base, very tightly set in the area where the ribs disappeared. Under strong magnification the surface is rough, forming elevations in spiral direction.

Aperture sub-oval; columella barely arched, with an internal columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Figure 17. *Pyrgulina permanens* n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,45 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratipo, 2,14 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); C: la misma concha de la fig. B en vista apical; D: protoconcha; E-H: microescultura y detalles.

Figura 17. Pyrgulina permanens n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,45 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratipo, 2,14 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); C: la misma concha de la fig. B en vista apical; D: protoconcha; E-H: microescultura y detalles.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.45 x 0.95 mm; h = 1.40 mm; A = 0.78 mm.

Remarks: See comments in *Pyrgulina pirinthella* and in *Pyrgulina lineotuber* n. sp.

Pyrgulina tenerrima (Melvill, 1906) described from the Gulf of Oman and cited from Viet Nam, Vanuatu, Fiji and the Solomon Islands, has a much smaller protoconch (230 μ m), it has a higher spire and the profile of the whorls is more stepped, the ribs are about three times narrower than their interspaces, the aperture is much smaller (A = 25% H compared with 32% in *P. permanens* n. sp.), the columellar tooth is conspicuous and the aperture has spiral cordlets inside.

Pyrgulina lineotuber n. sp. (Figure 18)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 18A); Aqaba, 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35054 (exCER). *Paratypes:* Jordan • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200055 (exCER) • 1 s; Aqaba, "Marine station"; 18 m; MZB60239.

Material examined (3 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name alludes the microsculpture which covers the entire surface with spiral lines of tubercles.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of Jordan, Aqaba, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute (<1.5 mm) but solid, subcylindrical, vitreous white, not very shiny. Protoconch rather high, type C, with a diameter of about 210 μ m. Teleoconch with three stepped whorls, with a relatively fast growth, slightly convex, the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Spire moderately high. Suture shallow, with an obvious subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture formed by 12–14 ribs, of rounded in profile, prosocline, half as wide as their interspaces, not reaching the upper suture and fading out somewhat below the periphery of the last whorl. Spiral sculpture formed by equidistant spiral cords, much narrower than their interspaces. There are about 10 cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and about 6 more, almost negligible, on the base. There is a granular microsculpture

Pyrgulina cf. *minimalicii* Peñas & Rolán, 2017 has a larger shell although the protoconch is smaller (240 μ m), the spire is not so high (h = 55% H compared to 44% in *P. permanens* n. sp.), it is wider (H/D = 2.3), the ribs are extended conspicuously on the base to the aperture; it has more spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl and less at the base.

Pyrgulina quinqueflexa n. sp. has a shell of similar size, slightly higher, but with the same height it has almost one whorl more, with a slower growth of the whorls; the protoconch is smaller, the ribs reach the umbilical area and it has less spiral cords, although these are thicker and run over the ribs.

forming spiral lines on the entire surface of the teleoconch.

Aperture sub-oval; columella arched, opisthocline, with a pliciform, internal columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.4 x 0.54 mm; h = 0.82 mm; A = 0.43 mm.

Remarks: It may seem that *Pyrgulina permanens* n. sp. and this species are somewhat similar, but the former has a significantly larger shell and also the protoconch is larger; the spire is higher and the spiral sculpture is different; it has a subsutural shelf, the spiral cords are approximately as wide as their interspaces; there are about 12 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and on the base it has at least 15 evident spiral striae.

Pyrgulina congressa Peñas & Rolán 2017, described from the continental shelf of Fiji and the Solomon Islands, has a similar shell profile and is also

Figure 18. *Pyrgulina lineotuber* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.4 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: protoconch; C-E: microsculpture.

Figura 18. *Pyrgulina lineotuber* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,4 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: protoconcha; C-E: microescultura.

minute, but it is wider ($H/D = 2$), the suture is deep, the ribs are thin, much narrower than their interspaces, with an angular profile and it lacks a columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina? problematica Hornung & Mermod, 1924, described from Massawa, Red Sea, also has a minute shell, but has a strong carina on the edge of the shoulder, which is angular, and it only has 9 ribs per whorl, much narrower than their interspaces, prolonged conspicuously to the aperture; the spiral sculpture is formed by narrow and tightly set grooves.

Pyrgulina quinqueflexa n. sp. looks like this species with more whorls, but it has a much larger shell, and also the protoconch is larger, the growth of the whorls is slower, the last whorl is rounded at the periphery, the ribs, although attenuated, are prolonged on the base to the aperture, the spiral cords override the ribs and the columellar tooth is more conspicuous.

Pyrgulina tenerrima (Melvill, 1906) (see ROBBA *ET AL.*, 1993) has a larger shell, with whorls distinctly stepped, the ribs are narrower, the spiral cordlets are feeble and there is no spiral microsculpture.

Pyrgulina microtuber n. sp. (Figures 19, 20)

Chrysallida pirintella [sic] - AARTSEN ET AL. 1989, *Boll. Malacol.* 25 (1-4): 70; 74, fig. 5; ZENETOS ET AL., 2004. *CIESM Atlas of. Ex. Spec.*, p.140-141.

Pyrgulina cf. *pirinthella* - GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL., 2014: fig. 220.

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 19A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35055 (exCER). *Paratypes*: Jordan • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200056 (exCER) • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS (100646) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; CAP.

Material examined (10 s): The type material and Egypt • 4 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is from the word “micro”, beginning of the “microscopic”, and the Latin word *tuber, eris* “protuberance”, alluding to the very small tubercles which cover all the surface of the shell.

Distribution: Infralittoral of Egypt and Jordan, Red Sea.

Description: Shell very small (<2.0 mm) but solid, subcylindrical, milk white, shiny. Protoconch of type C, with a diameter of about 240 μ m. Teleoconch with 3.5 slightly convex whorls, the last one broadly rounded at the periphery. Spire rather high (h = 55% H). Suture deep with a clear subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture formed by 14-16 robust ribs, rather angular in profile, slightly prosocline, nearly half as wide as their interspaces, extended conspicuously on the base to the aperture. Spiral sculpture formed by thin, equidistant cordlets, almost as wide as their interspaces, about 6 on the first whorl, 9 on the second, 18-20 between sutures at the beginning of the last one, of which 4-5 tightly packed on the shoulder, and 7-8 more on the base. Under strong magnification, the surface appears rough, mainly in the area between the ribs, and it is formed by very dense granules and tubercles, loosely arranged in spiral direction, but not forming lines.

Aperture narrow, sub-elliptic; columella slightly curved, with a columellar tooth not prominent but obvious. Outer lip slightly thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.8 x 0.78 mm; h = 1 mm; A = 0.57 mm.

Remarks: See comments in *Pyrgulina pirinthella* and in *Pyrgulina adducta*.

As previously mentioned, AARTSEN ET AL. (1989), ZENETOS ET AL. (2004) and

GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014) figured several shells from the Eastern Mediterranean similar to *Pyrgulina pirinthella*, which we believe to be more coincident with our *P. microtuber* n. sp.

Pyrgulinna wesselinghi (Robba, 2013), a Middle Miocene fossil species described from Central Java, Indonesia, has a shell of similar profile and dimensions, but it has more clearly stepped whorls, a shorter spire (h= 60% H) without an evident shoulder, and fewer spiral cords, only 10-11 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl and 5-6 on the base.

Pyrgulina minimalicii Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of New Caledonia, Fiji, Solomon Islands and Philippines, has a higher protoconch tending to type B and larger (between 270 and 290 μ m in diameter), the teleoconch whorls are more convex, the last one almost angular at the periphery, the ribs are very thin, sharp-edged, not reaching the base of the aperture, and it lacks a columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina nugatoria (Hedley, 1903), described from the circalittoral of Australia, has a more fragile shell, larger, narrower, with a very stepped profile, with a very wide shoulder; it has more ribs which are wider than the interspaces and the aperture is larger and wider.

Pyrgulina minusgranum n. sp. has a shell which is proportionally smaller, wider, has fewer axial ribs faded below the periphery of the last whorl and the

Figure 19. *Pyrgulina microtuber* n. sp., A: holotype, 1.8 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratype, 1.53 mm, same locality (MNHN); C: protoconch of the paratype; D, E: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 19. Pyrgulina microtuber n. sp., A: holotipo, 1,8 mm de altura, Aqaba, Jordania, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratipo, 1,53 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); C: protoconcha del paratipo; D, E: microescultura y detalle.

spiral sculpture consists in grooves instead of cordlets.

Pyrgulina scabra n. sp. has a smaller shell though the protoconch has a larger diameter; it is sub-oval, has a shorter spire ($h = 62\% h$), the last whorl is rounded at the periphery, the ribs do not reach the aperture and it has only 8-9 spiral cords between

sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and 5-6 more on the base. When examined under strong magnification, the microsculpture of that species is seen to consist of parallel lines (contrary to the microsculpture of *P. microtuber* which is formed by granules, sometimes fused but not by lines).

Pyrgulina scabra n. sp. (Figure 21)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 21A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35056 (exCER).

Paratypes: Jordan • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35057 (exCER).

Material examined (3 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin adjective *scabrus*, *bra*, *brum* which means “rough” alluding to its surface.

Distribution: Infralittoral of Jordan, Aqaba.

Description: Shell minute (<1.5 mm) but solid, sub-oval, vitreous white, somewhat shiny. Protoconch type C with a diameter of about 250 μ m. Teleoconch with three stepped, convex whorls, with a low spire and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, undulating, with a conspicuous subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture formed by 14 very robust ribs, rounded in profile, prosocline, almost equal to their interspaces, prolonged attenuated on the base. Spiral sculpture present only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by equidistant spiral cords, narrower than their interspaces, except on the shoulder where they are more closely set; there are about 9 on the penultimate whorl and between sutures at the beginning of the last one, and 5-6 more on the base. Under strong magnification, there is a rather regular microsculpture of spiral lines and not of tubercles or granules.

Aperture small, sub-oval; columella arched, opisthoclinal, without a visible columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.40 x 0.72 mm; h = 0.9 mm; A = 0.5 mm.

Remarks: See Remarks in *Pyrgulina microtuber* n. sp.

Spiralinella? discreta Thiele, 1926, described from Indonesia, also has a tiny shell, but somewhat narrower, with a more sub-cylindrical profile, the ribs are weak, orthoclinal, and disappear attenuated at the periphery of the last whorl; the spiral sculpture is formed by almost microscopic spiral grooves, more marked on the base and there is a conspicuous columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina excellenter Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of Fiji, has a tiny shell, similar profile, somewhat wider, the whorls are more convex, the last one rounded at the periphery, and the sculpture is different: it has about 18 less robust ribs, spiral sculpture is formed by many more spiral cordlets, about 14 in the penultimate whorl, 18 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, plus 10-12 very tight on the base.

Chrysallida brenda A. Adams, 1860, described from Japan, has a conical profile but is larger with the same number of whorls; instead of a shoulder it has a narrow but well marked subsutural shelf; it has more ribs (18-20) less robust, orthoclinal, which disappear attenuated at the periphery of the last whorl and it has a visible columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina quasicylindrica Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of Vanuatu, Fiji and the Solomon Islands, has a tiny shell, with an almost cylindrical profile, the ribs are twice as narrow as their interspaces, conspicuously prolonged to the aperture, the spiral sculpture overruns the ribs, and it is formed by five cords on the penultimate whorl and between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl.

Pyrgulina minusgranum n. sp. also has a that is tiny shell, very robust, sub-cylindrical, with more rapid growth of the whorls, the suture is deeper, canaliculate, with a subsutural shelf, between sutures the spiral cords are of the same width as their interspaces, on the base they overrun the ribs; the aperture is semicircular, with a continuous peristome and the outer lip is thickened.

See comments in *Pyrgulina microtuber* n. sp.

Figure 20. *Pyrgulina microtuber* n. sp. A, B: shells, 1.6, 1.35 mm in height, Abu Ghusum (MZB); C-E: shells in apical view, protoconch; F-H microsculpture and detail.

Figura 20. Pyrgulina microtuber n. sp. A, B: conchas, 1,6, 1,35 mm de altura, Abu Ghusum (MZB); C-E: conchas en vista apical, protoconcha; F-H microescultura y detalle.

Pyrgulina minusgranum n. sp. (Figure 22)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Figs. 22A-B); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-37058 (exCER). *Paratypes*: Jordan • 3 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-37059 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200057 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MZB60240 (exCER) • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100647 (exCER).

Material examined (16 s): The type material and Egypt • 7 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; CAP (exCER).

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is from the Latin word: the adverb *minus*, which means “smaller”, and *granum*, which means “seed”, alluding to its small size.

Figure 21. *Pyrgulina scabra* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.4 mm, Jordan, Aqaba Gulf, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratype, 1.5 mm, same locality (MNHN); C: protoconch of one paratype; D-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 21. *Pyrgulina scabra* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,4 mm, Jordania, Golfo de Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratipo, 1,5 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); C: protoconcha de un paratipo; D-F: microescultura y detalle.

Figure 22. *Pyrgulina minusgranum* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 1.04 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); C: protoconch; D, E: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 22. *Pyrgulina minusgranum* n. sp. A, B: holotipo, 1,04 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); C: protoconcha; D, E: microescultura y detalle.

Distribution: Known in the infralittoral of Jordan and Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute (<1.5 mm) but very robust, subcylindrical, vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch of type C, relatively wide, with a diameter of almost 300 µm. Teleoconch with 2 ½ convex whorls of rapid growth, with a very short spire, almost stepped in profile, and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture very deep, canaliculate, with a narrow subsutural shelf.

Axial sculpture formed by about 14 elevated ribs, of rounded profile,

somewhat narrower than their interspaces, prolonged conspicuously to the aperture. Spiral sculpture present only in the interspaces of the ribs between sutures, but overriding the ribs on the base; there are about 8-9 cords, approximately as wide as their interspaces, on the penultimate whorl and between sutures at the beginning of the last one, and 5 more on the base. Under strong magnification, a spiral microsculpture is seen on the cords, but not in their interspaces nor on the ribs.

Aperture small, semicircular, with a continuous peristome; columella almost straight, opisthoclinal, tooth not apparent but there is a small internal columellar fold. Outer lip very thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.04 x 0.51 mm; h = 0.73 mm; A = 0.37 mm.

Remarks: See comments in *Pyrgulina scabra* n. sp.

Pyrgulina quasicylindrica Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water

of Vanuatu, Fiji and Solomon Islands has a strong resemblance to this species: its dimensions, the sub-cylindrical profile of the shell, the continuous peristome and the thickened outer lip, but we believe that they are different species: *P. quasicylindrica* has narrower ribs, half as wide as their interspaces, has fewer spiral cords, about 5 on the penultimate whorl, which override the ribs, the aperture is wider and the protoconch is somewhat smaller.

Pyrgulina condita n. sp. (Figure 23A-E)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s; (Fig. 23A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35060 (exCER). *Paratypes:* Jordan • 2 s (Fig. 23 B); same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35061 (exCER) • 3 s; same data as for holotype; MZB (exCER) • 3 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200058 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100649 (exCER) • 3 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (17 s): The type material and Jordan • 3 s; Aqaba Gulf; MZB.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is from the past participle of the Latin verb *condo*, which means “put together, join” alluding to the fact that we are putting together shells in order to describe the species.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the Gulf of Aqaba, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute (<1.4 mm) but solid, subcylindrical. Vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch type C with a diameter of about 290 μ m. Teleoconch with 2.5 slightly convex whorls, with a moderately high spire and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, canaliculate with a narrow subsutural shoulder.

Axial sculpture formed by about 14 rather thick ribs, almost half as wide as their interspaces, arched, almost opisthoclinal, which disappear attenuated at the periphery of the last whorl. Spiral sculpture also conspicuous, formed by 6 spiral cords present only in the interspaces of the ribs since the first whorl, nearly half as wide as their interspaces; in some shells the first subsutural cord is weaker or obsolete; there are 6-7 more spiral cords on the base.

Aperture sub-oval; columella arched, opisthoclinal, with a pliciform columellar tooth placed very backward. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.15 x 0.52 mm; h = 0.71 mm; A = 0.40 mm.

Remarks: This tiny species does not agree with the description or illustration of *Pyrgulina nana* Hornung & Mermod, 1924 nor with the illustrations (always tentative) of ÖZTÜRK ET AL. (2006, as *Chrysallida micronana* n. nov.), GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL. (2014: 74) or LINDEN & EIKENBOOM (1992, as *Chrysallida* spec. C). *Pyrgulina nana* has a sub-oval shell, somewhat narrower, the whorls are almost flat, the ribs are straight, rather prosoclinal, prolonged on the base, the spiral sculpture does not cover the entire whorl, and there is only one cord on the upper whorl.

Chrysallida roberti Dance & Eames, 1966, a Holocene fossil species described from southeastern Iraq, has a shell of similar dimensions (the holotype examined by the authors, NHMUK 196526, measures 1.0 x 0.5 mm) but has a more sub-oval profile, with convex whorls, the last one bellying, the suture is shallow, the ribs (13) have a rounded profile, there are only 3-4 spiral cords between sutures, and only in the lower half of the whorls.

Figure 23. A-E. *Pyrgulina condita* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1.15 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B, C: paratipo, 1.12 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); D: protoconcha del holotipo; E: microescultura. F-G. *Pyrgulina* cf. *pretiosa* (W.H. Turton, 1932). F: concha, 1 mm, Egipto, Abu Ghusum (MZB); G: microescultura.

Figura 23. A-E. Pyrgulina condita n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,15 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B, C: paratipo, 1,12 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); D: protoconcha del holotipo; E: microescultura. F-G. Pyrgulina cf. pretiosa (W.H. Turton, 1932). F: concha, 1 mm, Egipto, Abu Ghusum (MZB); G: microescultura.

Parthenia punctigera A. Adams, 1860, described from Japan, has a similar sculpture, 5 spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl plus a subsutural thickening as a step, plus 6 grooves on the base, but the profile of the shell is truncate-conical, it measures 1.7 mm with one whorl more, the last whorl is angled at the periphery and the ribs are prolonged on the base to the aperture.

Parthenina plurifuniculata Peñas & Rolán, 2017 described from deep water of Vanuatu, Solomon Islands and Marquesas Archipelago, also has a tiny shell, of similar dimensions (1 x 0.5 mm), but has a more truncate-conical profile, the whorls are flat-convex, the last one very angular at the periphery, the spiral sculpture covers the $\frac{3}{4}$ parts of the whorls, being absent on the suture and the base.

Pyrgulina cf. pretiosa (W. H. Turton, 1932) (Figure 23F-G)

Odostomia pretiosa Turton, 1932. *The marine shells of Port Alfred, S. Africa*: 102, pl. 22, fig. 739.

Type material: Not examined.

Other material examined (2 s): Jordan • 1 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS. Egypt • 1 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Port Alfred, South Africa.

Distribution: Described from South Africa and recorded by FUKUDA (1995) from Japan. It is recorded here by first time from Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: In TURTON (1932).

Dimensions of the figured shell: 1 x 0.6 mm; h = 0.75 mm; A = 0.44 mm.

Remarks: Our identification of this species is tentative because we have not seen the type material, but our shells exactly coincide with that illustrated in FUKUDA (1995: p.28, fig. 1021) as *Chrysallida (Pyrgulina) pretiosa*.

See comments in *P. erecta* n. sp.

Pyrgulina lacrima n. sp. (Figure 24A-D)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 24A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35062 (exCER). *Paratypes:* Jordan • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35063 (exCER) • 4 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200059 (exCER) • 3 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MZB60242 (exCER).

Material examined (12 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name alludes the conical form of the shell like a tear, from the Latin *lacrima, ae*.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Red Sea.

Description: Shell very small (<2 mm), almost minute, solid, sub-oval tending to sub-cylindrical, vitreous, white, bright. Protoconch type C, with a diameter of about 280 μ m. Teleoconch with more than three flat-convex whorls, with a slightly elevated spire, rather broadly rounded at the periphery of the last whorl. Suture deep, canaliculated, with a narrow subsutural shelf.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 robust ribs, almost rectangular in profile, orthocone or slightly prosocline, equal or somewhat narrower than their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture. Spiral sculpture only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by cords, nearly equidistant, narrower than their interspaces, 8-9 in the penultimate whorl and 9-10 between sutures at the beginning of the last one, and 10 more on the base, narrowing towards the aperture

Figure 24. A-D. *Pyrgulina lacrima* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.87 mm in height, Aqaba, Jordan, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratype, 1.58 mm, same locality (MNHN); C: other paratype, same locality (MNHN); D: protoconch. E-J. *Pyrgulina erecta* n. sp. E: holotype, 2.4 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); F: paratype, 1.86 mm, same locality; G: other paratype, same locality; H: protoconch; I, J: sculpture and detail.

Figura 24. A-D. Pyrgulina lacrima n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,87 mm de altura, Aqaba, Jordania, 5–15 m (MNHN); B: paratipo, 1,58 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); C: otro paratipo, misma localidad (MNHN); D: protoconcha. E-J. *Pyrgulina erecta* n. sp. E: holotipo, 2,4 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); F: paratipo, 1,86 mm, misma localidad; G: otro paratipo, misma localidad; H: protoconcha; I, J: escultura y detalle.

Aperture sub-oval; columella arched, opisthocline, with a conspicuous columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.87 x 0.9 mm; h = 1.32 mm; A = 0.81 mm.

Remarks: *Pyrgulina maiae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924 has a much larger shell comparing adult specimens, is cyrtocoid, with a higher spire (h = 50% H compared to about 65% in *Pyrgulina lacrima* n. sp.) and higher H/D ratio (2.5

compared to about 2.1), the suture is shallow, not canaliculate and the aperture is proportionally smaller.

Pyrgulina collectitia Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of Vanuatu, Fiji, Solomon Islands and the Marquesas Archipelago, has a shell of similar profile and dimensions, but has a shoulder instead of a subsutural shelf, has fewer spiral cords which partly override the ribs, and has a smaller and narrower aperture.

Pyrgulina erecta n. sp. (Figure 24E-J)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 24E); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35064 (exCER). *Paratypes:* Jordan • 5 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35065 (exCER) • 5 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200060 (exCER) • 5 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100649 (exCER) • 5 s; same data as for holotype; MZB60243 (exCER) • 5 s, 17 j; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (82 s, 20 j): The type material and Jordan • 17 s; Aqaba; CBS. Egypt • 18 s; Hurg-hada; 10–30 m; MHNS • 4 s, 2 j; Abu Ghusum; CBS • 1 j; Zabargad; 27 m; MZB • 7 s; Wadi Gimal; 16 m; CBS. Sudan • 3 s; Mesharifa; Stn A1; MZB. Eritrea • 1 s; Dahlak; CBS. Saudi Arabia • 3 s; Jedda; sample 46 (478); MZB • 3 s; Jedda; sample 96 (436); MZB.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is from the Latin word *erectus* which means “erect”.

Distribution: Common in the infralittoral of all the Red Sea.

Description: Shell small (<3 mm), solid, of variable size, regularly conical, vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch type C with a diameter between 270 and 290 μ m. Teleoconch with 4–5 flat or flat-convex whorls, with a low spire. Suture deep, undulating.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 robust ribs, rounded in profile, prosocline, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, with an adapical bulge which gives a wavy profile to the suture, like a shoulder, and prolonged attenuated on the base down to the aperture. Spiral sculpture only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by cords narrower than their interspaces, almost equidistant except for a small gap below the adapical bulge of the rib; there are 8–9 on the penultimate whorl, 10–12 between sutures at the beginning of the last one and about 10 more on the base.

Aperture sub-oval, small; columella arched, opisthocline, with a distinct, but

not prominent columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.4 x 1.1 mm; h = 1.35 mm; A = 0.76 mm.

Remarks: *Pyrgulina maiae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924 has a shell of similar dimensions, but in our opinion they are two different species. Comparing adult shells, *Pyrgulina maiae* is sub-oval, narrower (H/D = 2.5 versus 2.2 in *P. erecta* n. sp.), the whorls are more convex, the last one broadly rounded at the periphery, the ribs are orthocline, there are fewer spiral cords between sutures and more on the base, and the aperture is narrower.

Pyrgulina satistriata Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of New Caledonia and Solomon Islands, has a very robust, wider shell (H/D = 1.8), more angular at the periphery of the last whorl, with the base slightly concave. It has more spiral cords both between sutures and on the base, and these are wider than their interspaces. The columellar tooth is very prominent and there are 6 spiral cords visible inside the outer lip.

Pyrgulina exoleta Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of New Caledonia, Vanuatu, Solomon Islands and the Philippines, has a shell of similar profile but smaller, the spire is shorter, the whorls flat-convex, the last one rather rounded at the periphery; it has fewer ribs and fewer spiral cords, 6 on the penultimate whorl and 8 between sutures on the last one.

Pyrgulina pretiosa (W. H. Turton, 1932) may be similar to juvenile shells of *P. erecta* n. sp. We have examined and compared several samples and we found some differences: the shell of *P. erecta* is narrower, the ribs are orthocone, they do not have an evident subsutural step like that of *P. pretiosa*, the aperture is smaller and there is no umbilicus (see above).

Pyrgulina collecticia Peñas & Rolán 2017 (Figure 25)

Pyrgulina collecticia Peñas & Rolán, 2017. *Soc. Esp. Malac., ECIMAT*, Vigo, p. 217-218, figs 11A, 66F-H.

Type material examined. *Holotype*: Solomon Islands • 1 s (Fig. 25A); N Buena Vista I.; 08°40'S, 160°04'E; 396–411 m; SALOMON I.; stn DW1762; MNHN-IM-2000-32125. *Paratypes*: Solomon Islands • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-32126.

Other material examined (2 s): Jordan • 1 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS (exCER). Sudan: • 1 s; Mesharifa; Stn A2; MZB.

Type locality: Solomon Islands, N Buena Vista I., 08°40'S, 160°04'E, 396-411 m.

Distribution: Known in deep water of the Marquesas Archipelago, Vanuatu, Fiji and Solomon Is. It is recorded here for first time from the infralittoral of Jordan and Sudan, Red Sea.

Description: In PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017). Shell small (<2.5 mm), not very solid, pupoid, milky white, shiny. Protoconch type C with a diameter of about 250 µm. Teleoconch with four flat to flat-convex whorls, with a low spire and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, with a narrow subsutural shelf.

Axial sculpture formed by about 16 elevated ribs, almost quadrangular in profile, orthocone, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture, with an adapical bulge which gives a wavy profile to the suture. Spiral sculpture formed by almost equidistant cords, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, about 10 on the penultimate whorl and between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and 10 more on the base, more closely set next to the aperture. Under strong magnification, a microsculpture is observed in the interspaces of the spiral cords, formed by small punctures.

Aperture pyriform, narrow, peristome continuous; columella opistho-

cone, almost straight, with a clear columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the larger shell figured: 2.3 x 0.97 mm; h = 1.2 mm; A = 0.73mm.

Remarks: *Pyrgulina maiae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924 has a more robust shell, rather large and also the protoconch has a larger diameter, the shape is cyrtocoenoid, the ribs have a rounded profile, the aperture is sub-oval with a non-continuous peristome.

Pyrgulina verticalis Peñas & Rolán, 2017 described from deep water of New Caledonia, Vanuatu and Solomon Islands, also has a pupoid profile and similar dimensions, but is wider, the whorls are more convex, the suture is deeper, canaliculate, there are fewer ribs which are twice as narrow as its interspaces, the aperture is sub-elliptical, very opisthocline.

Pyrgulina tutubaensis Peñas & Rolán, 2017 described from deep water of Vanuatu, has a also pupoid shell, but much smaller, minute, the whorls are more convex, the suture is canaliculate, there are only 6 spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl and 8 grooves on the base.

Figure 25. *Pyrgulina collecticia* Peñas & Rolán, 2017. A: shell, 2.3 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); B, C: shell, 1.93 mm, Sudan, Mesharifa (MZB); D: protoconch; E, F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 25. *Pyrgulina collecticia* Peñas & Rolán, 2017. A: concha, 2,3 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); B, C: concha, 1,93 mm, Sudán, Mesharifa (MZB); D: protoconcha; E, F: microscultura y detalle.

Pyrgulina linomicalii n. sp. (Figure 26)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 26A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35273. *Paratypes*: • 5 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35274 (exCER) • 4 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/00096 (exCER) • 4 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100661 (exCER) • 5 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Figure 26. *Pyrgulina linomicalii* n. sp. A: holotype, 3.13 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B, C: paratypes, 3.93, 3.1 mm in height, (MNHN); D, E: protoconchs; F–H: sculpture and detail.

Figura 26. *Pyrgulina linomicalii* n. sp. A: holotipo, 3.13 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B, C: paratipos, 3.93, 3.1 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); D, E: protoconchas; F–H: escultura y detalle.

Material examined (92 s): The type material and Jordan • 55 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS and CAP (exCER) • 4 s, Aqaba, “Marine Station”; 18 m; MZB. Egypt • 8 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS • 3 s; Zabargad; 17 m; MZB. Saudi Arabia • 3 s; Jedda; sample 96 (436); MZB.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Pasquale Micali, known Italian Malacologist, who helped us in many works, including this one.

Distribution: Common in the infralittoral of the Red Sea. BOSCH ET AL. (1995, fig. 798) recorded it from the East Arabian coast, under the name *Chrysallida* cf. *fischeri*.

Description: Shell solid, conical, cyrtocoenoid in the adapical part, milky white. Protoconch of type C, with a diameter of about 280 μ m. Teleoconch with 5–6 slightly convex whorls, with a rather high spire and the last whorl rounded at the periphery. Suture shallow, undulating.

Axial sculpture formed by about 22 orthocone ribs, approximately equal in width to their interspaces or slightly narrower, slightly thickened at their adapical end. Spiral sculpture formed by cordlets, about eight in the spire whorls, about 10 between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and about 15 more on the base.

Aperture oval; columella arched with a prominent columellar tooth. Not umbilicated. In some shells, three or four internal spiral ridges can be observed.

Dimensions of the holotype: 3.13 x 1.2 mm; h = 1.5 mm; A = 0.9 mm.

Remarks: The species *Pyrgulina linomicalii* n. sp. is characterized by its uniformly elongate high spire, the axial

sculpture formed by orthocone axial ribs, the rather dense spiral sculpture in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by numerous spiral cords wider than their interspaces. Also, an oval aperture and prominent columellar tooth.

Pyrgulina maiae Hornung & Mermod, 1924 has a smaller shell with the same number of whorls, being proportionally wider, with a less elevated spire; the spiral cords are narrower than their interspaces; the columellar tooth is much less prominent, the aperture lacks internal spiral ridges, and under strong magnification the surface appears covered with microperforations.

Pyrgulina fischeri Hornung & Mermod, 1925, in our opinion is not a *Pyrgulina* but a *Pyrgiscus* (*Turbonillini*), because its protoconch is of the type B. Furthermore, the shell is smaller and narrower (H/D = 3 in compared to 2.6 in average in *P. linomicalii*), has fewer ribs which are narrower, and narrower than their interspaces, the aperture is narrow with a pliciform columellar tooth and it lacks internal spiral ridges.

Pyrgulina pupaeformis (Souverbie & Montrouzier, 1865) (see pl. 5, Fig. 4 of the original description). This shell appears to have a more curved outline, and to be slightly larger.

Pyrgulina prosoribs n. sp. (Figure 27)

Type material. *Holotype:* Sudan • 1 s (Fig. 27A); Mesharifa; Stn A2; MZB60244.

Material examined (1 s): The type material.

Type locality: Sudan, Mesharifa.

Etymology: The specific name alludes the position of the axial ribs which are prosocline.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality, in the Red Sea.

Description: Shell small (<2.5 mm), not very solid, conical to cyrtocoenoid, milk white. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of 300 μ m. Teleoconch with

five slightly convex whorls, a rather high spire (h <55% H), and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, with a narrow shoulder whose border forms a kind of belt on the adapical part of the ribs.

Figure 27. *Pyrgulina prosoribs* n. sp. A, B: holotype, 2.3 mm, Sudan, Mesharifa, Stn A2 (MZB); C: protoconch; D, E: sculpture and detail.

Figura 27. *Pyrgulina prosoribs* n. sp. A, B: holotipo, 2,3 mm, Sudán, Mesharifa, Stn A2 (MZB); C: protoconcha; D, E: escultura y detalle.

Axial sculpture formed by about 20–22 robust ribs, rounded in profile, prosocline, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture. Spiral sculpture formed by thin, equidistant cords, much narrower than their interspaces, 5 on the first two whorls, 6 on the third and 8 on the penultimate and between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, and about 10 more on the base including the peripheral one.

Aperture small ($A < 30\% H$), semicircular; columella slightly arched, with a prominent columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.3 x 0.85 mm; h = 1.2 mm; A = 0.64 mm.

Remarks: *Pyrgulina bertae* Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from the circalittoral of the Marquesas Archipelago, has a shell of similar dimensions and profile, but has one whorl less with the same height, the suture is canalculated, the ribs are fewer and as wide as its interspaces, the spiral cords are thicker, also as wide as their interspaces, and the protoconch is smaller (about 250 μm in diameter).

Noemia arctelirata de Folin, 1878, described from the infralittoral of the Andaman Islands, has a larger and wider shell; the syntype examined (MNHN 24474) measures 3.3 mm with 5 ½ whorls of teleoconch, the last whorl is rounded at the periphery, it has more ribs (24), much wider than their interspaces and the spiral sculpture formed by grooves is almost imperceptible.

Noemia arctelirata de Folin, 1878, described from the infralittoral of the Andaman Islands, has a larger and wider shell; the syntype examined (MNHN 24474) measures 3.3 mm with 5 ½ whorls of teleoconch, the last whorl is rounded at the periphery, it has more ribs (24), much wider than their interspaces and the spiral sculpture formed by grooves is almost imperceptible.

Odostomia densecostata Garrett, 1873, described from the infralittoral of Viti (now Fiji) Islands (type material ANSP58110 examined by the authors), has a larger shell, with very convex whorls, the last one rounded at the periphery, has fewer ribs, about 18, rounded, much wider than their interspaces, and the spiral sculpture is

formed by many spiral grooves, about 20 on the penultimate whorl.

Pyrgulina maiae Hornung & Mermod, 1924 has a wider shell, it is larger, with one whorl less; the last whorl is rounded at the periphery, the ribs are more robust, orthocone, and are as wide as their interspaces; and under strong magnification the surface is covered by punctures.

Pyrgulina maiae Hornung & Mermod, 1924 (Figures 28, 29)

Pyrgulina maiae Hornung & Mermod, 1924. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St. Natur. Genova*, 51: 296-297.

Pyrgulina maiae - SAURIN, 1959. *Ann. Fac. Sci. Saigon*, 247, pl. 4, fig. 16; - GIANNUZZI-SAVELLI ET AL., 2014: 74, fig. 216-217.

Chrysallida maiae - VAN AARTSEN, 1977. *Conchiglie*, 13: 54, fig. 12.; VAN DER LINDEN & EIKENBOOM, 1992. *Basteria*, 56: 41, fig. 54; BUZZURRO & GREPPI, 1995. *Notiz. CISMA*, 17: 8-9 figs. 7-8; NOFRONI & TRINGALI, 1995. *Notiz. CISMA*, 24-28, pls. 1-2; ZENETOS ET AL., 2004. *CIESM Atlas of Ex. Spec.*, p. 138-139.

Type material: Figuration of the holotype in BUZZURRO & GREPPI (1995).

Other material examined (83 s): Jordan • 20 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS • 2 s; Aqaba “Marine station”; 18 m; MZB. Egypt • 12 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS • 7 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB • 13 s; Zabargad; 17–28 m; MZB • 12 s; Wadi Gimal; 16 m; MZB. Eritrea • 6 s; Dahlak; MZB. Sudan • 6 s; Mesharif; stn A2; MZB. Saudi Arabia • 5 s; Jeddah; sample 96 (436); MZB.

Type locality: Massawa, Eritrea.

Distribution: Species common in the infralittoral of the Red Sea and East Mediterranean. SAURIN (1959) recorded it from Vietnam.

Description: En HORNING & MERMOD (1924), LINDEN & EIKENBOOM (1992), NOFRONI & TRINGALI (1995) and ZENETOS ET AL. (2004). Shell small, cyrtocoid, solid. Milk white. Protoconch type C with a diameter of about 290 μ m. Teleoconch with up to 5 slightly convex whorls, with a moderately high spire ($h = 50\% H$), and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 elevated ribs, rounded in profile, orthocone, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, prolonged on the base to the aperture. Spiral sculpture, only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by 7 cords on the penultimate whorl and 9-10 between sutures at the beginning of the last one, narrower than their interspaces, plus about 12 on the base. Under strong magnification the surface is covered by numerous microperforations.

Aperture pyriform; columella arched, with a conspicuous columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

The larger shell figured is 2.7 x 1.05 mm; $h = 1.37$ mm; $A = 0.83$ mm.

Remarks: See comments in *Pyrgulina prosoribs* n. sp., *P. lacrima* n. sp., *P. erecta* n. sp., *P. linomicalii* n. sp. and *P. collecticia* Peñas & Rolán, 2017.

See remarks in NOFRONI & TRINGALI (1995). Contrary to the opinion of PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017), probably *P. maiae* may be different from *P. pupaeformis*. We have found two shells (Figure 29A-B) which present some differences from the typical form of *P. maiae*: a more conical profile, the whorls are more convex, the last one is rounded at the periphery, has more spiral cords between sutures and less on the base; but when these differences come from a single shell we have opted not to describe it as a new species, keeping it as a form of *P. maiae* (1.86 mm).

Figure 28. *Pyrgulina maiae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924. A, B: shells, 2.55, 2.7 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba (MHNS); C: protoconch; D-F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 28. *Pyrgulina maiae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924. A, B: conchas, 2,55, 2,7 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba (MHNS); C: protoconcha; D-F: microescultura y detalle.

Figure 29. *Pyrgulina* cf. *maiae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924. A, B: shell, 1.86 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba (MHNS); C-E: apex, protoconch and detail; F, G: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 29. *Pyrgulina* cf. *maiae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924. A, B: concha, 1,86 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba (MHNS); C-E: ápice, protoconcha y detalle; F, G: microescultura y detalle.

Pyrgulina craticulata (Issel, 1869) (Figure 30A-E)

Odontostomia craticulata Issel, 1869. *Malac. Mar Rosso*, Pisa: 180.

Type material examined. *Syntype*: • 1 s (SAVIGNY, 1817, pl. 3 fig. 39); Red Sea; MNHN-IM-2000-34095.

Other material examined (29 s): Jordan • 11 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS • 9 s; Gulf of Aqaba; MZB. Egypt • 2 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; CAP • 1 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB • 6 s; Zabargad; 36 m; MZB.

Type locality: Red Sea.

Distribution: Subfossil and Recent, common in the infralittoral and circalittoral of the Red Sea.

Description: En ISSEL (1869). Illustration in BOUCHET & DANRIGAL (1982: fig. 75).

The syntype examined measures 2.05 mm.

The larger shell of our material measures 1.8 x 0.8 mm; h = 1 mm; A = 0.62 mm.

Remarks: *Pyrgulina canalicia* Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of the Solomon Islands, has a smaller shell with the same number of whorls, it is wider (H/D = 1.9 versus 2.2 on *P. craticulata*), the whorls are flat-concave, the last one is obviously angled at the periphery, between sutures the spiral sculpture is weaker and on the base has numerous spiral striae.

Pyrgulina alicae Hornung & Mermod, 1924 (Figure 30H-J)

Pyrgulina alicae Hornung & Mermod, 1924. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St. Natur. Genova*, 51: 299, fig.14.

Type material: Not examined.

Material examined (5 s): Jordan • 3 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS (exCER). Egypt • 2 s; Zabargad; 36 m; MZB.

Type locality: Eritrea, Massawa, 30 m depth.

Distribution: Eritrea, Jordan and Egypt in the Red Sea.

Description: In HORNUNG & MERMOD (1924). Shell minute but solid, truncate-conical, milk white, shiny. Teleoconch with three flat whorls, a short spire, and the last whorl angular at the periphery. Suture deep, canaliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by about 16 robust ribs, nearly rectangular in profile, orthocline, approximately as wide as their interspaces, prolonged to the aperture. Spiral sculpture formed by a cord located just above the suture, forming nodules at the intersection with the ribs and delimiting depressions between these and the lower suture. In the interspaces of the ribs there are about 10 spiral striae and at least about 15 on the base.

Aperture sub-oval, arched, opisthoclinal, reflected to outside forming an umbilical chink. Columellar tooth late. Outer lip not thickened.

The larger shell figured is 1.57 x 0.75 mm; h = 0.95 mm; A = 0.57 mm.

Remarks: SAURIN (1959) included this species in the genus *Egilina*, but in our opinion it should be maintained in the genus *Pyrgulina*. In the species of the genus *Babella* (= *Egilina*), the axial ribs are interrupted at the periphery of the last whorl or earlier, while in *Pyrgulina alicae* the ribs are extended to the base, although attenuated. HORNUNG & MERMOD (1924) did not observe the spiral microsculpture between the ribs and into the base, but we believe that our shells refer to this species.

Parthenina spiculiformae Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from the circalittoral in French Polynesia, has a narrower conical shell with a higher spire, the suture is also narrow, hardly canaliculate; there are more ribs, around 20, and there is no spiral sculpture between the ribs nor on the base.

Pyrgulina lamyi Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, described from the infralittoral of Indo-China, has a slightly larger shell (1.7 mm), with one whorl

more, the whorls are flat-convex, the last one is quite rounded at the periphery, there are two spiral cordlets below the

peripheral cord on the last whorl and no spiral sculpture between the ribs nor on the base.

Genus *Chrysallida* Carpenter, 1857

Odostomia (*Chrysallida*) Carpenter, 1857. *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*, 24: 170. Type species (by original designation): *Chemnitzia communis* C.B. Adams, 1852 [Recent: Mazatlan, Pacific coast of Mexico].

Shell small, solid, with axial sculpture and spiral in all the teleoconch whorls, of approximately equal thick-

ness, forming nodules at its junction; on the base, the spiral sculpture predominates. Protoconch of type B or C.

Chrysallida yamaniaensis n. sp. (Figure 30K-M)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 30K); Aqaba, Yamania; 2 m; MZB60245.

Material examined (1 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, Yamania, 2 m.

Etymology: The specific name is that of the locality where the species was collected.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute (<1.2 mm) but very robust, pupoid, whitish, somewhat shiny. Protoconch of type C with a diameter of about 220 μ m. Teleoconch with three flat-convex whorls, with a moderately high spire and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, slightly canaliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by about 16 robust ribs, orthocline, forming thick nodules at the intersection with the spiral cords; below the periphery of the last whorl, the ribs are faded and become confused with the growth lines. Spiral sculpture formed by three cords on the first whorl, including the less conspicuous subsutural one, four cords between sutures on the penultimate whorl, the peripheral cord and four more cords on the base of the last whorl.

Aperture small, sub-oval; columella slightly curved, opisthoclinal, with a clear columellar tooth. Outer lip thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.15 x 0.58 mm; h = 0.73 mm; A = 0.31 mm.

Remarks: This species is very characteristic, being very small and with an ovoid profile.

Chrysallida malayana Thiele, 1925, described from Malaysia, has a sub-oval shell and also nodose at the intersection of the ribs and the spiral cords, but is significantly higher (2.3 mm) and narrower, the whorls are more convex, the suture is deep but not canaliculate, and on the base the axial sculpture predominates.

Odostomia tomacula (Laseron, 1951), described from the infralittoral of Australia (holotype C.36516 in Australian Museum of Sydney, examined) has a larger shell, more truncate-conical in profile, the whorls are convex, the last one rounded at the periphery, with a concave base, the suture is very deep, with a wide subsutural shelf and although the sculpture is similar the spiral cords scarcely mounted on the ribs.

Genus *Costabieta* Laseron, 1956

Costabieta Laseron, 1956. *Austr. J. Mar. & Freshw. Res.*, 7: 421. Type species: *Costabieta paucina*, Laseron, 1956, by original designation [Recent: Michaelmas Cay, Queensland].

Figure 30. A-G. *Pyrgulina craticulata* (Issel, 1869). A, B: syntype, 2.0 mm (MNHN); C-E: shells, 1.8, 1.32, 1.66 mm, Jordan, Aqaba (MHNS); F, G: apical view and protoconch. H-J. *Pyrgulina alicae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924. H, I: shells, 1.57, 1.39, mm, Jordan, Aqaba (CBS); J: sculpture. K-M. *Chrysallida yamaniaensis* n. sp. K: holotype, 1.15 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 2 m (MZB); L: protoconch; M: detail of the sculpture.

Figura 30. A-G. *Pyrgulina craticulata* (Issel, 1869). A, B: sintipos, 2,0 mm (MNHN); C-E: conchas, 1,8, 1,32, 1,66 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, (MHNS); F, G: vista apical y protoconcha. H-J. *Pyrgulina alicae* Hornung & Mermod, 1924. H, I: conchas, 1,57, 1,39 mm, Jordania, Aqaba (CBS); J: escultura. K-M. *Chrysallida yamaniaensis* n. sp. K: holotipo, 1,15 mm, Aqaba, Jordania, 2 m (MZB); L: protoconcha; M: detalle de la escultura.

The shells of *Costabieta*, which look indeed like *Rissoina*, are distinguished by their great robustness, as if formed by overlapping layers, with strong spiral and axial ribs, by having a thick-

ened outer lip and a peculiar microsculpture on the entire teleoconch which produces a rough surface, and by a weak or absent columellar fold. Protoconch of type C.

Costabieta favrei (Hornung & Mermod, 1925) (Figure 31)

Pyrgulina (Ividella?) favrei Hornung & Mermod, 1925. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St.*, 52: 28-29, fig. 5.
Chrysalida (Ividella) massuensis Selli, 1973. *Doc. Paleon., parte seconda*: 342, pl. XX, fig. 9a, 9b.
Costabieta horrida (Garret, 1873) – BLATTERER, 2019: 398, plate 210, fig. 9a, b. (misidentification)

Type material: Holotype of *Pyrgulina favrei*, not examined.
Other material examined (46 s): Jordan • 4 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS • 5 s; Aqaba; sample (174); MZB • 5 s; Aqaba, Yamania; 2 m; MZB. Egypt • 1 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS • 4 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB • 1 s; Zabargad; 17 m; stn MR75; MZB • 6 s; Zabargad; stn MR75; MZB • 6 s; Zabargad; stn MR75; CAP (exMZB); Saudi Arabia • 12 s; MZB • 2 s; Jeddah; sample 48; MZB.
Type locality: Sarato Island and Massawa, Eritrea.

Distribution: Described from the infralittoral of the Red Sea, we observe that it is common throughout the Red Sea.

Description: In HORNUNG & MERMOD (1925) and in PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017).

Remarks: In PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017) this species was tentatively, but erroneously placed in the synonymy of *Costabieta horrida* (Garrett, 1873). *Costabieta portentosa* Peñas & Rolán, 2017 (p. 284-286, figs. 15B, 87A-G), described

from deep water of New Caledonia, Vanuatu and Marquesas Archipelago, is similar in sculpture and could even be conspecific, but differs in having a narrower aperture, resulting in a less conical and more fusiform profile, and also in having a different arrangement of the basal cords. Taking into account the difference in bathymetric range, they are kept as separate until more data are available.

Genus *Miralda* A. Adams, 1863

Miralda A. Adams, 1863. *Jour. Proc. Linn. Soc. London*, 7: 3. Type species: *Parthenia diadema* A. Adams, 1860, subsequent designation by VERRILL & BUSH, 1900, p. 530 [Recent: “Mino-Sima” (= Mishima Island, Sea of Japan)].

Species included here have shells with a moderately high spire, axial ribs present but rather weak and usually marked only in the upper part of the whorl, forming nodules at the crossing points with the spirals. The spiral sculpture is well-marked predominant over the axial, formed by two or more thick

cords between sutures, and additional cords on the base. The aperture has usually a thickened columella and, in many cases, also a thickened parietal callus. The protoconch is almost always of type A with a partly submerged nucleus, or type B; more rarely of type C.

Key of the species of the genus *Miralda*

- 1. - Protoconch of type B, with the nucleus not visible 2
- Protoconch of type A or type B with part of the nucleus exposed 3
- 2. - Shell conical, with axial riblets and one spiral cord on the base *protogalea*
- Shell subcylindrical, without axial riblets, two cords on the base *paulbartschi*

Figure 31. *Costabieta favrei* (Hornung & Mermod, 1925). A-C: shells, 2.9, 2.6, 2.1 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); D: apical view; E: protoconch; F, G: sculpture and detail.

Figura 31. *Costabieta favrei* (Hornung & Mermod, 1925). A-C: conchas, 2,9, 2,6, 2,1 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); D: visión apical; E: protoconcha; F, G: escultura y detalle.

- 3. - Shell sub-oval, protoconch type A, with the nucleus partly submerged, with four spiral cords on the base *elegans*
- Shell globose, protoconch type B, tending to A, with seven spiral cords on the base, plus the peripheral one *diadema*

Miralda protogalea Peñas & Rolán, 2017 (Figure 32A-F)

Miralda protogalea Peñas & Rolán, 2017. *Soc. Esp. Malac. ECIMAT*, Vigo, p. 312-313, figs. 16L, 98C-G.
Miralda protogalea – BLATTERER, 2019: 398, plate 210, fig. 13a, b.

Type material examined. *Holotype*: Vanuatu • 1 s; W Tutuba Island, Vunatavo Bay; 15°34'S, 167°16'E; 10–80 m; SANTO 2006; Stn DS103; MNHN-IM-2000-32196.

Other material examined (18 s, 4 j): Egypt • 7 s, 1 j; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS. Jordan • 1 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; CAP (exCER). Eritrea • 10 s, 3 j; Dahlak; MZB.

Type locality: Vanuatu, W Tutuba Island, Vunatavo Bay, 15°34'S, 167°16'E, 10-80 m.

Distribution: Infralittoral and circalittoral of Vanuatu, Solomon Islands, Fiji, and Marquesas Archipelago. It is here recorded for the first time from the Red Sea (Egypt, Jordan and Eritrea).

Description: In PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017).

Dimensions of the shells figured: 2.2 x 0.9 mm; h = 1.15 mm; A = 0.64 mm.

Remarks: We have not noticed any significant differences in the material studied, neither in the type of the protoconch, nor in its sculpture; we only have observed that the shells of the Red Sea are slightly narrower (H/D = 2.3 on average) and the protoconch has a slightly larger diameter.

Miralda cf. *paulbartschi* (Pilsbry, 1918) (Figure 32G-I)

Odostomia (*Miralda*) *paulbartschi* Pilsbry, 1918. *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philadelphia*, 60 (1917): 310, fig. 15.

Type material: Not examined.

Material examined (1 s): Egypt • 1 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS.

Type locality: North shore of Kahoolawe, Hawaii.

Distribution: Known in the infralittoral of Hawaii, it is recorded for the first time from the Red Sea.

Description: In PILSBRY (1918) and in KAY (1979: 409-410: fig. 132G). Shell small, solid, sub-cylindrical, milk white. Protoconch type B with a helmet form and a diameter of about 270 μ m. Teleoconch with five whorls with a serrated profile, with a rather high spire, and the last whorl angled at the periphery. Suture deep, canaliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by about 20 ribs, forming knobs at their junction with the spiral cords. Spiral sculpture formed by two upper nodular cords and a wider lower one, with a wavy profile, a thick cord, divided in two by a shallow groove, on the periphery of the last whorl, and two more cords on the base. Growth lines conspicuous, orthocline to opisthocline.

Aperture sub-oval; columella arched, opisthocline, with a clear but not prominent columellar tooth. No clear umbili-

cus, but a kind of umbilical chink is formed between the columella and the lower cord. Outer lip not thickened.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.3 x 0.95 mm.

Dimensions of the shell figured: 2.51 x 1 mm; h = 1.4 mm; A = 0.75 mm.

Remarks: The authors studied the Pyramidellidae of Hawaii, included in the work of SEVERNS (2011) and we think that the examined shells are coincident with those examined from the Red Sea.

This species has a great resemblance to *Miralda subtilstriae* Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from deep water of the Solomon Islands and the Marquesas Archipelago, but the latter is somewhat smaller, with a more conical profile and, above all, the protoconch is strongly carinate. *Miralda scopulorum* (Watson, 1886) has a more sub-oval profile and the protoconch is of type C with a spiral cord, the shell is smaller, with less whorls and riblets in its lower part.

Figure 32. A-F. *Miralda protogalea* Peñas & Rolán, 2017. A, B: shells, 2.07, 1.96, mm in height, Egypt, Hurghada, 10-30 m (MHNS); C, D: shells, 2.05, 1.8 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5-15 m (CAP); E: shell in apical position, Egypt, Hurghada, (MHNS); F: protoconch. G-I. *Miralda* cf. *paulbartschi* (Pilsbry, 1918). G: shell, 2.51 mm, Egypt, Hurghada, 10-30 m (MHNS); H: protoconch; I: detail of the sculpture.

Figura 32. A-F *Miralda protogalea* Peñas & Rolán, 2017. A, B: conchas, 2,07, 1,96, mm de altura, Egipto, Hurgada, 10-30 m (MHNS); C, D: conchas, 2,05, 1,8 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5-15 m (MHNS); E: concha en posición apical, Egipto, Hurgada (MHNS); F: protoconcha. G-I. *Miralda* cf. *paulbartschi* (Pilsbry, 1918). G: concha, 2,51 mm, Egipto, Hurgada, 10-30 m (MHNS); H: protoconcha; I: detalle de la escultura.

Miralda elegans (De Folin, 1870) (Figure 33A-E)

Mathilda elegans de Folin, 1870. *Les Fonds de la Mer*, 1: 212-213, pl. 28, fig. 15.

Type material. *Syntypes*: Guinea-Bissau • 2 s (figured by HOENSELAAR & MOOLENBEEK 1990: figs 3-5; not examined); Bissagos Archipelago, Cagnabac (currently Canhabaque Is.); MNHN-IM-2000-35082.

Other material examined (2 s): Jordan • 1 s; Gulf of Aqaba; MZB. Egypt • 1 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Cagnabac (currently Canhabaque Is.), Bissagos Archipelago, West Africa.

Distribution: Species abundant in the infralittoral and circalittoral of the African Atlantic, rare in the Mediterranean. It is here cited for the first time for the Red Sea, where 2 shells have been found.

Description: In DE FOLIN (1870). Shell minute (< 2 mm) but solid, sub-oval. Vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch quite obtuse, type A, with a diameter of about 180 μ m, with the nucleus submerged almost $\frac{3}{4}$ parts. Teleoconch of low spire, with three flat-convex whorls, the last one broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture shallow, hardly marked.

Axial sculpture formed by 14 thick ribs, of rounded profile, slightly opisthocline, which are interrupted towards the middle of the whorl, approximately as wide as their interspaces. Growth lines very numerous, showing a rough surface under strong magnification. Spiral sculpture on the upper part of the whorls formed by cords which override the ribs, forming nodules, 2 on the first whorl and sometimes a third somewhat obsolete on the last one; below them is an almost smooth spiral cord, hardly thickened, separated by a wide groove from a peripheral cord of equal thickness; on the base there are 4 more spiral cords, decreasing in size.

Aperture narrow, pear-shaped, with a continuous peristome; columella slightly arched, opisthocline, with an evident columellar tooth. Outer lip somewhat thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the shells figured: 1.65 x 0.75 mm and 1.5 x 0.66 mm.

Remarks: In addition to the material examined referred above, the authors studied the Pyramidellidae of the Western Africa and found in that area abundant shells of this species. HOENSELAAR & MOOLENBEEK (1990) cited it for the first time in the Mediterranean islands of Formentera, Baleares, Spain. Later PEÑAS & GIRIBET (2003) recorded it on the Garraf coast (NE Iberian Peninsula). We have not noticed any significant differences between the Red Sea and West African specimens, neither in the type of the protoconch, nor in the outline and sculpture of the teleoconch. This occurrence is puzzling. Mediterranean records are so scanty that an introduction from there into the Red sea is unlikely. A further possibility is that cryptic species are involved.

Miralda scopulorum (Watson, 1886) has a shell of similar dimensions and profile, but the protoconch is of type C and strongly carinate, it only has two pearly spiral cords, plus one smooth between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl and, on the base, there is only one spiral cord besides the peripheral.

Miralda umeralis (Hedley, 1902) (syntype in Australian Museum, C.12075, examined), was described from the infralittoral of Australia and recorded by MELVILL (1910) in deep water of the Gulf of Oman. It has a shell of similar profile but more robust, the protoconch is of type B, the axial cords are only two on all the whorls, also on the third one, and very nodose; the spiral cords, also those of the base, are wide, with a rounded profile.

Figure 33. A-E. *Miralda elegans* (De Folin, 1870). A: shell, 1.62 mm, Egypt, Abu Ghusum, (CBS); B: shell, 1.48 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, (CBS); C: protoconch of the last shell; D, E: microsculpture and detail. F-I. *Miralda diadema* (A. Adams, 1860); F, G: shells, 1.9, 1.8 mm, Egypt, Hurghada, 20-30 m (MHNS); H: apical view; I: microsculpture.

Figura 33. A-E. Miralda elegans (De Folin, 1870). A: concha, 1,62 mm, Egipto, Abu Ghusum, (CBS); B: concha, 1,48 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, (CBS); C: protoconcha de la última concha; D, E: microescultura y detalle. F-I. Miralda diadema (A. Adams, 1860); F, G: conchas, 1,9, 1,8 mm, Egipto, Hurgada, 20-30 m (MHNS); H: vista apical; I: microescultura.

Miralda diadema (A. Adams, 1860) (Figure 33F-I)

Parthenia diadema A. Adams, 1860. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 3 (5): 479.

Pyrgulina eximia Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907. *J. Conchyl.*, 54: 196-197, pl. 7, fig. 5. [Type locality: Annam, plage de Ben-Son, Indochina].

Odostomia (Miralda) syrptites Pilsbry, 1918. *Proc. Ac. Nat. Sci. Philadelphia*, 60 (1917): 318-319, fig. 12. [Type locality Eaikiki beach, Oahu, Hawaii] *new synonym*.

Odostomia (Miralda) diadema - DALL & BARTSCH, 1906. *Proc. U. S. Nat. Mus.*, 30: 356, pl. 17, fig. 2.

Miralda diadema - SAURIN, 1959. *Ann. Fac. Sci. Saigon*, p. 256, pl. 5, fig. 17.

Type material: not examined (syntype figured by HIGO ET AL., 2001: 125, fig. G4422)

Material examined (3 s): Egypt • 3 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS.

Type locality: Mino-Sima (= Mishima Island, Sea of Japan), 63 fathoms.

Distribution: Described from Japan, and recorded by several authors from Japan, Hawaii, Viet Nam (DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1907 and SAURIN, 1959), and Gulf of Aden (MELVILL, 1910).

Description: In DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER (1907) as *Pyrgulina eximia*. Shell very small (< 2 mm) but solid, very broad (H/D = 1.85), globose, tending to oval, milk white. Protoconch type B, with a helmet form, and with a diameter of about 230 µm, with the nucleus minimally visible. Teleoconch with three flat-convex whorls, with a short spire, the last whorl bulging, rounded at the periphery. Suture deep, canaliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by about 14 ribs on the early whorls and about 18 on the last one, nodose, predominant over the spiral sculpture, interrupted abruptly by a suprasutural cord in the upper whorls; on the last whorl there are two cords above the suture, the upper one somewhat nodose. Spiral sculpture formed, in addition to the suprasutural cords, by two adapical cords which form knobs at their intersection with the ribs

and bifurcate on the last whorl, giving rise to a third cord; last whorl with one additional smooth peripheral cord and 6 more cords on the base. Under strong magnification, thin axial wrinkles are seen on the main cord.

Aperture relatively large, sub-oval, with a continuous peristome; columella slightly arched, opisthocline, with an obvious columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened, inside which 5-6 spiral cords can be seen.

Dimensions of the figured shell: 1.85 x 1 mm; h = 1.35 mm; A = 0.75 mm.

Remarks: We have not found any other species close to the present one in the Indo-Pacific. According to MELVILL (1910), *Actaeopyramis brevicula* Melvill & Standen, 1903, is synonymous with *Miralda diadema*, however, when examining the two syntypes (NHMUK 1903.12.15.58-59) it can be noticed that they are obviously different species: *A. brevicula* is conical, has the whorls stepped, with 3 spiral cords on the first whorl, four between sutures at the beginning of the last one, badly defined ribs on which the spiral cords are mounted.

Genus *Oscilla* A. Adams, 1861

Oscilla A. Adams, 1861. *Ann. & Mag. Nat. Hist.*, series 3, 7: 296. Type species: *Monoptygma cingulata* A. Adams, 1861, by monotypy [Recent: Hulu-Shan bay, N. China].

= *Hinemoa* Oliver, 1915. *Trans. N. Zeal. Inst.*, 47 (1914): 531. Type species: *Hinemoa punicea* Oliver, 1915 by original designation [Recent: Kermadec Islands].

This genus includes small or tiny shells, with short, conical spire or cyrtocoid, with a spiral sculpture formed by strong cords and axial sculpture

limited to microscopic threads in the interspaces, and almost always with a columellar tooth in the aperture. Protoconch type A, B or C.

Key of the species of the genus *Oscilla*

1. - Axial sculpture present, conspicuously overriding the spiral cords, protoconch of type A *mirifica* n. sp.
 - Axial sculpture absent, or present only in the interspaces between the spiral cords 2
2. - Shell with two spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl 3
 - Shell with more than two spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl 4
3. - Base without axial sculpture between the cords *beccarii*
 - Base with one spiral cord, axial sculpture present between the cords *composita*
4. - With three spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl 5
 - with more than three cords between sutures at the beginning of last whorl 8
5. - Protoconch of type B, shell pyramidal *aqabaensis* n. sp.
 - Protoconch of type A 6
6. - Without axial sculpture between the spiral cords, on the base 4 cords plus the peripheral one *virginiae* n. sp.
 - With axial sculpture between the cords 7
7. - Shell pyramidal, protoconch with 2.5 whorls and an emerged nucleus *jocosa*
 - Shell conical, protoconch with the nucleus partly submerged *bellardii*
8. - Protoconch of type A, four or five spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of last whorl 9
 - Protoconch type C, shell cylindrical, four spiral cords *cylindrica*
9. - Four spiral cords between sutures at the beginning of last whorl *appeliusi*
 - Five spiral cords between sutures *multistriata* n. sp.

***Oscilla mirifica* n. sp. (Figure 34A-C)**

Type material. *Holotype:* Egypt • 1 s (Figs. 34A-B); Hurghada, 20-30 m; collected by diving; MNHN-IM-2000-35066 (exCER).

Material examined (1 s): The type material.

Type locality: Egypt, Hurghada, 20-30 m.

Etymology: The specific name is from the Latin word *mirificus, a, um* which means “surprising, admirable” alluding to the unusual characters of the shell.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Description: Shell minute (<2 mm), solid, conical-cylindrical, milky white, shiny. Protoconch type A with a diameter of about 230 µm, with a partly submerged nucleus. Teleoconch with four almost flat whorls, with a low spire and the last whorl rounded at the periphery. Suture shallow, not conspicuous.

Axial sculpture present all over the teleoconch, consisting of orthocline and rather widely separated riblets, numer-

ous and are more tightly set on the last whorl. Spiral sculpture formed by three cords in the three first whorls; the adapical one is less prominent, the second one is the most prominent and has more marked nodules, also present in the first one and less evidently in the lower one.

Aperture oval with the peristome rather ragged by the termination off the spiral cords; columella arched, opisthocline. Umbilicus inconspicuous.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 1.5 mm x 0.71 in diameter. (H/D = 2.11).

Remarks: There is no other species in the area with the characters present in this one.

Miralda scopulorum (Watson, 1886), described from the infralittoral of Hawaii (4 syntypes, NHMUK

1887.2.91526-29, examined) has a shell of similar profile and dimensions but the protoconch is of type C tending to B, and it also lacks the lamellar axial sculpture (which is conspicuous in *O. mirifica*).

Oscilla beccarii (Hornung & Mermod, 1924) (Figure 34D-G)

Cingulina (Odetta) beccarii Hornung & Mermod, 1924. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St. Nat. Genova*, 51: 303-304, fig. 19.

Oscilla (Hinemoa) beccarii - Saurin, 1958. *Contr. Inst. Oceanogr. Nhatrang*, 35: 79, pl. 3, fig. 14.

Type material examined. *Syntype:* Eritrea • 1 s; Massawa; 30 m deep; MCSNG 5799-5819.

Other material examined (20 s): Jordan • 10 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS (exCER) • 10 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; CAP (exCER).

Type locality: Eritrea, Massawa, 30 m deep.

Distribution: Infralittoral in the Red Sea. SAURIN (1958) recorded it from Viet Nam.

Description: In HORNUNG & MERMOD (1924) and in SAURIN (1958). Protoconch of type A with a diameter of about 220 μm , with the nucleus semi submerged. In some shells spiral cordlets can be observed in the inner part of the aperture. The syntype figured measures 1.75 mm.

Dimensions of the largest shell figured: 1.8 x 0.85 mm; h = 1.1 mm; A = 0.6 mm.

Remarks: This species is characterized by its conical profile, by the presence of two spiral cords by whorl, of which the lower one is half the width of the upper one, by the near absence of any evident axial sculpture between the

cords, and by the smooth base. It has a great resemblance to *Oscilla composita* Peñas & Rolán, 2017 described from the circalittoral of Vanuatu, but this has a protoconch with a smaller diameter (180 μm), the spiral cords have almost the same width, there is an evident axial sculpture between the cords and the base has two spiral cords in addition to the peripheral one.

Oscilla virginiae n. sp. has a shell of similar profile but smaller, a little wider, the protoconch is also smaller (180 μm in diameter), the upper spiral cords of the teleoconch starts bifurcating on the third whorl and again, more conspicuously, on the last one; there are four spiral cords on the base in addition to the peripheral one.

Oscilla composita Peñas & Rolán, 2017 (Figure 35A-E)

Oscilla composita. Peñas & Rolán, 2017. *Soc. Esp. Malac. ECIMAT*, Vigo, p. 327, figs. 17I, 103A-C.

Type material examined. *Holotype:* Vanuatu • 1 s; NW coast of Malo Island; 15°37'S, 167°04'E; 90-100 m; SANTO 2006; Stn EP28; MNHN-IM-2000-32208. *Paratypes:* • 3 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-32209.

Other material examined (19 s): Jordan • 7 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; CAP (exCER) • 1 s; Aqaba, "Marine Station"; MZB. Egypt • 10 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB. Sudan • 1 s; Sha'ab Rumi; 25 m; MZB.

Type locality: Vanuatu, NW coast of Malo Island, 15°37'S, 167°04'E, 90-100 m.

Distribution: Known from the infralittoral and circalittoral of Vanuatu, its distribution area is extended to the infralittoral of the Red Sea (Jordan, Egypt and Sudan).

Description: See PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017).

Remarks: See comments in *Oscilla beccarii* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924).

Figure 34. A-C. *Oscilla mirifica* n. sp. A-B: holotype, 1.5 mm in height, Egypt, Hurgada, 20-30 m (MNHN); C: protoconch. D-G. *Oscilla beccarii* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924). D: syntype, 1.75 mm (MCSNG); E, F: shells, 1.8, 1.77 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, (MHNS); G: shell in apical view, 1.65 mm, same locality.

Figura 34. A-C. *Oscilla mirifica* n. sp. A-B: holotipo, 1,5 mm de altura, Egipto, Hurgada, 20-30 m (MNHN); C: protoconcha. D-G. *Oscilla beccarii* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924). D: sintipo, 1,75 mm (MCSNG); E, F: conchas, 1,8, 1,77 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, (MHNS); G: concha en visión apical, 1,65 mm, misma localidad.

Oscilla aqabaensis n. sp. (Figure 35F-I)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 35F); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35067 (exCER). *Paratypes*: • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35068 (exCER).

Material examined (3 s): The type material.

Type locality: Red Sea, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The name of the present species is derived from Red Sea locality where it was collected and from where most of the studied material came.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Description: Shell small, very solid, conical and relatively wide, milky white, somewhat shiny. Protoconch of type B, in helmet form, with a diameter of about 200 μm . Teleoconch short with nearly four flat-convex whorls, the last one rounded at the periphery; suture hardly marked.

Axial sculpture only in the interspaces of the spiral cords, formed by numerous riblets, thin, very prosocline. Spiral sculpture formed by rounded cords, nearly equal in thickness, smooth; three in the spire whorls, four on the last whorl from suture to periphery, and five more on the base.

Aperture sub-oval; columella slightly curved, opisthoclinal, with a weak internal columellar tooth. Outer lip thickened. Not umbilicate.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.14 mm \times 1.11 mm (H/D: 1.93).

Remarks: *Oscilla jocosa* has a similar profile but the protoconch is of type A, with almost 2.5 whorls.

Oscilla solomonensis Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from the circalittoral of Solomon Islands, also has a similar shell profile, but the protoconch is of type C, the teleoconch has no visible axial sculpture, the columellar tooth is very prominent and there are spiral cordlets inside the aperture.

Oscilla tornata Melvill, 1893, described from the infralittoral and circalittoral of the Indian Ocean, has a much larger shell, the protoconch is of type B, tending to A, and it does not have a helmet shape; the spiral cords are of the same thickness, without any riblets in the spiral interspaces, the columellar tooth is prominent and there are spiral cordlets inside the aperture.

Odostomia (Evalea) lirata A. Adams, 1860, described from the infralittoral of Japan, has a much larger shell, with a higher spire, (H/D = 2.4), the axial ribs are hardly visible, orthoclinal, the aperture is pyriform, with a prominent columellar tooth and has inner spiral cordlets.

Oscilla virginiae n. sp. (Figure 36A-D)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 36A); Aqaba, 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35069 (exCER). *Paratypes:* • 4 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35070 (exCER) • 5 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200061 (exCER) • 3 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100650 • 5 s; same data as for holotype; MZB60246 (exCER) • 15 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (45 s): The type material and Jordan • 1 s; Aqaba, Yamanía; 2 m; MZB. Egypt • 9 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS • 2 s; Wadi Gimal; MZB.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Virginie Héros, Ingénieur d'Études in the MNHN, in recognition for her constant help in our work.

Distribution: Infralittoral of Jordan and Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small, solid, conical, milky white, shiny. Protoconch type A with a diameter of about 185–190 μm , with a partly submerged nucleus. Teleoconch with nearly 5 almost flat whorls, with a short spire and the last whorl rounded at the periphery. Suture shallow, inconspicuous.

Axial sculpture between the cords very slight, barely perceptible, confused with the growth lines which are prosocline. Spiral sculpture formed by two cords on the first and second whorls; on the third

one the upper cord, which is wider, begins to bifurcate, and on the penultimate whorl the two become very close together, at the end being three between sutures; plus a peripheral cord and 4 on the base.

Aperture pyriform; columella arched, opisthoclinal, with a prominent columellar tooth. Spiral cords somewhat visible inside the outer lip, which is not thickened. Not umbilicate, but with an umbilical chink in some shells.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.25 \times 1 mm; h = 1.35 mm; A = 0.75 mm.

Remarks: See comments in *Oscilla beccarii*.

Figure 35. A-E. *Oscilla composita* Peñas & Rolán, 2017. A-C: shells, 2.14 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); D: protoconch; E: microsculpture. F-I. *Oscilla aqabaensis* n. sp. F: holotype, 2.14 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); G, H: paratypes, 1.9, 2.0, mm, same locality (MNHN); I: protoconch.

Figura 35. A-E. *Oscilla composita* Peñas & Rolán, 2017. A-C: conchas, 2.14 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); D: protoconcha; E: microescultura. F-I. *Oscilla aqabaensis* n. sp. F: holotipo, 2.14 mm, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); G, H: paratipos, 1.9, 2.0 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); I: protoconcha.

Menestho (Oscilla) bellardii procera Selli, 1973, fossil from the Quaternary of Massaua, (compared with fig. 14, but fig. 13 is different) has a type B protoconch, the last whorl is angular at the periphery, the interspaces are equal to or wider than the cords, which do not have bifurcations on the previous whorls, and there are fewer spiral cords on the base.

Oscilla composita Peñas & Rolán, 2017, has a shell of similar profile but a little larger, the suture is visible, although hardly so, there is a conspicuous axial sculpture

between the spiral cords; these are not bifurcating in the subsutural area, but it is the peripheral cord that is bifurcated; on the base it has only two spiral cords.

Hinemoa duplex Laseron, 1959, described from the infralittoral of Australia, also has a shell in which the upper spiral cord bifurcates, but does so already from the second whorl, the shell is larger and narrow with the same number of whorls, the last whorl is angled at the periphery and has only two spiral cords on the base, in addition to the peripheral.

Oscilla jocosa Melvill, 1904 (Figure 36E-H)

Oscilla jocosa Melvill, 1904. *J. Malac.*, 11: 82-83, pl. 8, fig. 11.

Oscilla jocosa - DAUTZENBERG & FISCHER, 1907: 181-182, pl. 6, figs. 6-7; MELVILL, 1910: 194; SAURIN, 1959: 258, pl. 6, fig. 8; SAURIN, 1961: 253; PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2017: 336-338, figs. 18D, 107A-G.

Type material examined. *Syntypes*: Oman • 2 s (figured in PEÑAS & ROLÁN, 2017, figs. 107A-B); Gulf of Oman; 24°58'N, 56°54'E; 156 fms; NHMUK 1905.6.12.12-13.

Other material examined (18 s): Jordan • 8 s; Aqaba, 5–15 m; MZB • 1 s; Aqaba, 5–15 m; MHNS. Egypt • 7 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS • 1 s; Zabargad; 36 m; MZB. Saudi Arabia • 1 s; Jedda; sample 2 (548); MZB.

Type locality: Gulf of Oman, 24°58'N, 56°54'E, 156 fms.

Distribution: Known in the infralittoral and circalittoral of the Gulf of Oman, New Caledonia, Vanuatu, Solomon Islands and Vietnam. It is here cited for the first time from the Red Sea.

Description: In MELVILL (1904) and in PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017). The protoconch has an emerged nucleus of 2 ½ whorls. The teleoconch has the spiral sculpture formed by three thick cords between sutures of approximately equal thickness, almost equidistant; it has clear axial sculpture between the spiral cords formed by numerous thin riblets; the base has three spiral cords.

Dimensions of the figured shell: 1.9 x 0.93 mm; h = 1.1 mm; A = 0.62 mm.

Remarks: See remarks in *Oscilla virginiae* n. sp.

We reproduce here the comments in PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017: 338): “This species has been erroneously cited in the Eastern Mediterranean, as exotic, introduced from the Indian Ocean. It was reported for the first time in Mediterranean waters by AARTSEN, BARASH & CARROZZA (1989) and later recorded in AARTSEN (1994) and in ZENETOS ET AL. (2004), recognizing that it has not been found in the Red Sea. However, the Mediterranean species (from which there are several specimens in the collection of the first author) is a different species: it has a larger, more slender shell with the protoconch of type B and the two upper spiral cords are nodose”.

Oscilla bellardii (Hornung & Mermod, 1924) (Figure 37)

Cingulina (Odetta) bellardii Hornung & Mermod, 1924. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St. Nat.*, Genova, 51: 302-303, fig. XVIII.

Oscilla bellardii – BLATTERER, 2019: 401, plate 212, fig. 18a, b.

Figure 36. A-D. *Oscilla virginiae* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.25 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B, C: paratypes, 1.94, 1.7 mm, same locality (MNHN); D: protoconch. E-H. *Oscilla jocosa* Melvill, 1904. E, F: shells, 1.9, 1.72 mm, Jordan, Aqaba (MHNS); G: apex and protoconch; H: microsculpture.

Figura 36. A-D. *Oscilla virginiae* n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,25 mm de altura, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B, C: paratipos, 1,94, 1,7 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); D: protoconcha. E-H. *Oscilla jocosa* Melvill, 1904. E, F: conchas, 1,9, 1,72 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, (MHNS); G: ápice y protoconcha; H: microescultura.

Type material examined. *Syntypes*: Eritrea • 1 s (2.3 mm high); Massawa; 30 m deep; MCSNG 6205-6238 • 1 s (1.4 mm high); Massawa; 30 m deep; MCSNG 6293-6317.

Other material examined (11 s): Jordan • 2 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS • 7 s; Gulf of Aqaba; CBS. Egypt • 2 s; Abu Ghusum; CBS.

Type locality: Massawa, Eritrea, 30 m deep.

Distribution: Common in the infralittoral and circalittoral of the Red Sea.

Description: In HORNUNG & MERMOLD (1924). Protoconch of type A with a diameter of about 230 µm, with the nucleus partially submerged.

Remarks: The original description of this species induced us in error, since in their Figure 18, the authors illustrate an immature shell, and it is described as measuring 1.2 mm and with a more pyramidal shell profile. However, the

Figure 37. *Oscilla bellardii* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924). A: syntype, 1.4 mm, Massawa, Eritrea (MCSNG); B, C: shell, 1.8 mm, Aqaba Gulf (CBS); D: shell, 1.6 mm, same locality (MHNS); E: apex and protoconch; F, G: microsculpture.

Figura 37. *Oscilla bellardii* (Hornung & Mermod, 1924). A: syntype, 1,4 mm, Massawa, Eritrea (MCSNG); B, C: concha, 1,8 mm, Golfo de Aqaba (CBS); D: concha, 1,6 mm, misma localidad; E: ápice y protoconcha; F, G: microescultura.

largest of the two examined syntypes is an adult shell with dimensions of 2.3 mm, which agrees with our material.

The shells from Aqaba (MHNS) have a more conical profile but without other differences; this species has some simi-

larity in its form with *Oscilla marquesensis* Peñas & Rolán, 2017, but the latter has a different protoconch with 2 ½ whorls with the nucleus totally emerged and on the base have four spiral cords in addition to the peripheral one.

Oscilla cylindrica (de Folin, 1879) (Figure 38A-E)

Jaminea cylindrica de Folin, 1879. *Les fonds de la Mer* (1878): 206, pl. 9 fig. 5.

Hinemoa cylindrica – BUZZURRO, HOARAU, GREPPI & PELORCE, 2001. *Boll. Malac.*, 37 (1-4): 23-26.

= *Oscilla galilae*, Bogi, Kharan & Yokes, 2012. *Iberus*, 30 (2): 1-6, fig. 1A-F.

Type material: Probably lost (BUZZURRO *ET AL.* 2001). The holotype and one paratype of *Oscilla galilae* are figured in BOGI *ET AL.* (2012).

Other material examined (15 s): Jordan • 3 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS • 5 s; Aqaba; MZB. Egypt • 6 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; CAP (exCER); 1 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Borneo (South China Sea).

Distribution: BUZZURRO *ET AL.* (2001) recorded this species from the Philippines, from Mayotte in the Indian Ocean and as introduced in SE Turkey, Eastern Mediterranean. It is recorded here for the first time from the Red Sea.

Description: In DE FOLIN (1879), and in BOGI *ET AL.* (2012) as *Oscilla galilae*.

Dimensions of the figured shell: 1.6 x 0.64 mm; h = 1 mm; A = 0.52 mm.

Remarks: To date, this species had not been cited from the Red Sea. We believe that *Oscilla galilae* (Bogi, Kharan & Yokes, 2012: fig. 1A-F) is synonymous with *Oscilla cylindrica*, an Indo-Pacific

species which has been introduced into the Eastern Mediterranean. We do not find any differences between this species and our material from the Red Sea, in the SEM photographs examined. BOGI *ET AL.* (2012) dismissed the name *Oscilla cylindrica* as *nomen dubium*, and noted some differences between their material and the original description, but we prefer to still use the older name because the records reported by BUZZURRO *ET AL.* (2001) indicate a very broad distribution in the Indo-Pacific, compatible with the type locality in the South China Sea.

Oscilla appeliusi (Hornung & Mermod, 1925) (Figure 38F-G)

Cingulina (*Odetta*) *appeliusi* Hornung & Mermod, 1925. *Ann. Mus. Civ. St. Nat., Genova*, 51: 30, fig. 6.

?*Menestho* (*Oscilla*) *appeliusi* – SELLI, 1973. *Doc. Paleon., parte seconda*: 349, pl. XX, figs 11a-b, 12a-b.

Oscilla appeliusi – BLATTERER, 2019: 401, plate 212, fig. 17a, b.

Type material examined. *Syntypes:* Somalia [Somaliland] • 2 s; Zeila Archipelago, Sacadin Is.; MCSNG 5572-5579, 5607-5615 • 1 s (Fig. 38F); Zeila Archipelago, Sacadin Is.; NHMUK.

Other material examined (3 s): Egypt • 2 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS • 1 s; Zabargad; stn 1; MZB.

Type locality: Zeila archipelago, "Ile de Saldadin" (Sacadin Is.), Somalia [Somaliland].

Distribution: Scarcely found in the infralittoral and circalittoral of Eritrea and Egypt, Red Sea.

Description: IN HORNUNG & MERMOD (1925). Shell very small, sub-oval, solid. Protoconch type A tending to B, with a diameter of about 180 μ m, with the nucleus only 1/3 emerged. Teleoconch with four flat-convex whorls, a short spire and the last whorl rounded at the periphery. Suture shallow, not apparent.

Axial sculpture formed by numerous riblets, very tightly set, slightly prosocline, confused with the growth lines.

Spiral sculpture formed by 2 cords in the first whorl, three in the second and third whorls, of which the central one is narrower, and 4-5 cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, plus the peripheral and four on the base.

Aperture pyriform; columella arched, opisthocline, with a robust columellar tooth. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the figured shell: 1.8 x 0.75 mm; h = 1.1 mm; A = 0.57 mm.

Remarks: Another synonym of this species could be *Menestho* (*Oscilla*) *stefanisi* Selli, 1973.

Figure 38. A-E. *Oscilla cylindrica* (de Folin, 1879). A, B: shells, 1.6, 1.33 mm, Egypt, Hurghada, 10-30 m (MHNS); C: apical view, same locality (MHNS); D: detail of the sculpture; E: protoconch. F-H. *Oscilla appeliusi* (Hornung & Mermod, 1925). F: syntype, 1.5 mm, Somalia, Zeila (MCSNG); G: shell, 1.8 mm, Egypt, Hurghada, 10-30 m (MHNS); H: detail of the sculpture of the same shell.

Figura 38. A-E. *Oscilla cylindrica* (de Folin, 1879). A, B: conchas, 1,6, 1,33 mm, Egipto, Hurgada, 10-30 m (MHNS); C: vista apical, misma localidad (MHNS); D: detalle de la escultura; E: protoconcha. F-G. *Oscilla appeliusi* (Hornung & Mermod, 1925). F: sintipo, 1,5 mm, Somalia, Zeila (MCSNG); G: concha, 1,8 mm, Egipto, Hurgada, 10-30 m (MHNS); H: detalle de la escultura, misma concha.

Figure 39. *Oscilla multistriata* n. sp. A: holotype, 2.3 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B–D: paratypes, 1.95, 2.3, 2.0 mm, same locality (MNHN); E: apex and protoconch; F, G: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 39. *Oscilla multistriata* n. sp. A: holotipo, 2,3 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B–D: paratipos, 1,95, 2,3, 2,0 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); E: ápice y protoconcha; F, G: microescultura y detalle.

Oscilla multistriata n. sp. (Figure 39)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 39A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; in sediments, collected by diving; MNHN-IM-2000-35071 (exCER). *Paratypes*: Jordan • 3 s (Figs. 39B–D); same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35072 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200062 (exCER) • 2 s; same data as for holotype; MHNS 100651 (exCER) • 13 s; same data as for holotype; MZB60247 (exCER) • 4 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (32 s): The type material and Egypt • 2 s; Hurghada; 10–30 m; MHNS • 3 s; Wadi Gimal; CBS • 1 s; Abu Ghusum; CBS. Eritrea • 1 s; Dahlak; CBS.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name refers to the very fine and numerous riblets in the spaces between the spiral cords.

Distribution: Infralittoral of Egypt, Jordan, and Eritrea, Red Sea.

Description: Shell small (<2.5 mm), solid, cyrtoconoid, milky white, shiny. Protoconch type A tending to B, with a diameter of about 180 µm, with the nucleus only 1/3 emerged. Teleoconch with 4.5 flat-convex whorls with a wavy profile, with a rather elevated spire and the last whorl broadly rounded at the periphery. Suture shallow, not apparent.

Axial sculpture formed by numerous riblets, very tightly set, only visible under strong magnification, slightly prosocline, several of which override the cords, confused with the growth lines. Spiral sculpture formed by well-marked cords, almost rectangular in profile, which are three on the first two whorls, later are bifurcated and become 4–5 on the penultimate whorl; there are 5 cords between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl, somewhat narrower than their interspaces, plus the peripheral and five or six on the base.

Aperture pyriform; columella slightly arched, opisthocline, with a prominent columellar tooth. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 2.3 × 0.96 mm; h = 1.45 mm; A = 0.73 mm.

Remarks: *Oscilla multifuniculi* Peñas & Rolán, 2017 described from deep water of Vanuatu and the Solomon Islands, has a certain similarity with *Oscilla multistriata* n. sp. in its profile, but it is smaller, measuring 1.65 mm with the same number of whorls; the suture is apparent although not marked; it has fewer spiral cords: two on the first and second whorls, three in the penultimate and four between sutures at the beginning of the last one, plus the peripheral and 2–3 on the base.

Odostomia (Odetta) felix Dall & Bartsch, 1906, described from Japan, has a narrower shell (H/D = 2 in front to 2.3 in *Oscilla multistriata*) with a clearly conical profile, between sutures at the beginning of the last whorl only has four spiral cords and the spiral sculpture is more conspicuous.

Hinemoa voorwindei Laseron, 1959, described from the infralittoral of Australia, has a sub-oval shell, somewhat smaller, the whorls are more convex, the suture is deep, visible, the spiral cords are wider than their interspaces, it lacks any axial sculpture and the columellar tooth is weak and internal.

Genus *Pseudoscilla* Boettger, 1901

Pseudoscilla Boettger, 1902. Type species by monotypy: *Oscilla (Pseudoscilla) miocaenica* Boettger, 1902 [Kostej (now Coşteiu de Sus), Romania, Upper Miocene].

=*Miraldiella* Cossmann, 1921. Type species by original designation: *Odostomia (Parthenia) exarata* Carpenter, 1856 [Mazatlan, western Mexico, Recent].

Shell very small, similar to the genus *Oscilla*, conical or subcylindrical, characterized by having two or three spiral cords between sutures

forming sharp keels, with delicate axial riblets in the interspaces; without visible columellar tooth. Protoconch of type B.

Figure 40. *Pseudoscilla montseromansae* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.03 mm, Hurghada, Egypt, 10-30 m (MNHN); B: paratype, 1.04 mm, same locality (MNHN); C: paratype, apical view (MNHN); D: protoconch; E: sculpture.

Figura 40. *Pseudoscilla montseromansae* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,03 mm, Hurgada, Egipto, 10-30 m (MNHN); B: paratipo, 1,04 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); C: paratipo, vista apical (MNHN); D: protoconcha; E: escultura.

Pseudoscilla montseromansae n. sp. (Figure 40)

Type material. *Holotype:* Egypt • 1 s (Fig. 40A); Hurghada; 10–30 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35073 (exCER). *Paratypes:* Egypt • 3 s (Fig. 40B); same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35074 (exCER).

Material examined (4 s): The type material.

Type locality: Hurghada, Egypt, 10-30 m.

Etymology: This species is after Montserrat Romans Mediavilla, from Barcelona, a relative of the first author.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute (<1.2 mm), very fragile, subcylindrical, proportionally wide, vitreous white, shiny. Protoconch of type B tending to C, with a

diameter of about 220 µm. Teleoconch with three whorls and a moderately high spire. Suture not deep but marked.

Spiral sculpture formed by two cords per whorl, very sharp and prominent, plus one more sharp cord on the last whorl pro-

longing the suture and two on the base. At the beginning of the first whorl only, there are hardly conspicuous spiral grooves, but no axial sculpture. From the second whorl onwards, an axial sculpture can be seen between the spiral cords, formed by thin, almost equidistant ribs; however, under strong magnification, a spiral microsculpture may be seen in the interspaces of the cords.

Aperture small, semicircular; columella curved, opisthoclinal, without a distinct columellar tooth; outer lip sharp. No umbilicus, but a narrow umbilical chink can be seen next to the columella.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.03 x 0.62 mm; h = 0.65 mm; A = 0.4 mm.

Remarks: PEÑAS & ROLÁN (1999) have studied this genus from the coasts of West Africa and also Eastern America, and illustrated a specimen of the type species *Pseudoscilla miocaenica* (Boettger, 1901). None of these species has similarity with our species of the Red Sea. Neither does *Pseudoscilla bussanensis* Sosso, Dell'Angelo & Bonfitto, 2009, species from the Pliocene of the Ligurian area. Common to all species known from this genus is that none of them has a type A protoconch.

Genus *Babella* Dall & Bartsch, 1906

Babella Dall & Bartsch, 1906. *Proc. U. S. Nat. Mus.*, 30: 347. Type species: *Turbonilla (Babella) caelator* Dall & Bartsch, 1906 (unnecessary replacement name for *Parthenia caelata* A. Adams, 1863, non *Turbonilla caelata* Gould, 1861), by original designation [Recent: Japan].

= ? *Egilina* Dall & Bartsch, 1906. *Proc. U. S. Nat. Mus.*, 30: 354. Type species: *Parthenia mariella* A. Adams, 1860, by original designation [Recent: Mino-Sima, Japan].

= *Numaegilina* Nomura, 1938. *Saitô-Hô-on Kai Museum Res. Bull.*, 16: 65. Type species: *Chrysallida (Numaegilina) gloria* Nomura, 1938, by original designation [Recent: Japan].

= *Paregila* Laseron, 1951. *Rec. Austr. Museum*, 22 (4): 312. Type species: *Odostomia (Pyrgulina) henni* Brazier, 1894, by original designation [Recent: Watsons Bay, Sydney, Australia].

The genus *Babella* includes species with a solid shell, regular conical profile, axial sculpture formed by robust and very oblique ribs, interrupted by a thick spiral cord which runs above the suture determines a deep groove on the

periphery of the last whorl. A spiral microsculpture may exist in the interspaces and on the base. The aperture has a strong, pointed columellar tooth. Protoconch type A, B or C.

Key for the species of the genus *Babella*

1. - Protoconch of type A 2
 - Protoconch of type C tending to B 4
2. - With spiral sculpture between the ribs 3
 - Without spiral sculpture between the ribs, shell conical, ribs very prosocline *mariellaeformis*
3. - Shell pyramidal, ribs very prosocline *prominens*
 - Shell sub-oval or conical, ribs arched *ovalis* n. sp.
4. - With spiral sculpture on the base 5
 - Without spiral sculpture on the base, the ribs reach the lower suture *miconodulosa* n. sp.
5. - With spiral microsculpture between ribs, which are about 24, very prosocline *nimiaprocostae* n. sp.
 - Without spiral microsculpture between the ribs, which are about 18, less prosocline *maestratii* n. sp.

Figure 41. *Babella mariellaeformis* (Nomura, 1938). A, B: shell, 2.35 mm in height, Dahlak, Eritrea (MZB); C: apex; D, E: detail of the microsculpture.

Figura 41. *Babella mariellaeformis* (Nomura, 1938). A, B: concha, 2,35 mm de altura, Dahlak Eritrea (MZB); C: ápice; D, E: detalle de la microescultura.

Babella mariellaeformis (Nomura, 1938) (Figure 41)

Chrysallida (*Miralda*) *mariellaeformis* Nomura, 1938. *Saito Hō-on Kai Mus. Res. Bull.*, 16: 64-65; pl. 12, figs. 101a, 101b.

Type material: Not examined. Holotype (HT: SHK 8264) figured in HIGO *ET AL.* (2001).

Material examined (5 s): Eritrea • 2 s; Dahlak; MZB. Sudan • 2 s; Mesharifa; Stn A1 MZB. Egypt • 1 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB.

Type locality: Shiogama Bay, Miyagi Prefecture, north-eastern Honshū, Japan.

Distribution: Recent and fossil in Japan, where it is common. It is recorded here by first time in the Red Sea.

Description: In NOMURA (1938) and HORI (1996: 45, fig. 8). Protoconch of type A, with a diameter of 210 μm , with the nucleus partly submerged.

Dimensions of the shell figured: 2.35 x 1.1 mm.

Remarks: Even though the type material has somewhat larger dimensions,

we do not notice essential differences with our material: regularly conical shell, protoconch type A, with a partly submerged nucleus, suture deep, canaliculate; ribs distinctly prosocline, robust, approximately as wide as their interspaces, not reaching the lower suture but abutting on a suprasutural cord; ribs also do not reach the upper suture; there is no spiral sculpture in the interspaces of the ribs and there is a prominent columellar tooth.

Babella prominens Peñas & Rolán, 2017 (Figure 42)

Babella prominens Peñas & Rolán, 2017. *Soc. Esp. Malac. ECIMAT*, Vigo: p. 349-350, figs. 19B, 111A-E.

Type material examined. *Holotype*: Vanuatu • 1 s; S. of Santo; 15°38'S, 167°03'E; 140–182 m; MUSORSTOM 8; Stn CP1131-1132; MNHN-IM-2000-32224.

Other material examined (4 s): Jordan • 3 s; Aqaba; 5–15 m; MHNS. Egypt • 1 s; Abu Ghusum; MZB. **Type locality**: Vanuatu, S. of Santo, 15°38'S, 167°03'E, 140-182 m.

Distribution: Described from deep water of Vanuatu, it is recorded for the first time from the infralittoral of the Red Sea.

Description: In PEÑAS & ROLÁN (2017).

Dimensions of one of the figured shell: 1.6 x 0.9 mm; h = 1 mm; A = 0.57 mm.

Remarks: We have not noticed any significant differences between the shells from Vanuatu and those from the Red Sea of this tiny species, neither in the dimensions, nor in the profile, nor in the type of protoconch or in the sculpture; we have only noticed that the Red Sea shells are somewhat wider (H/D = 1.8 versus 2 in the holotype).

Babella ovalis n. sp. (Figures 43A, 44A, B)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 43A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35075 (exCER). *Paratypes*: Jordan • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200063 (exCER) • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MZB60248 (exCER) • 1 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (4 s): The type material.

Type locality: Aqaba, Jordan, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name alludes the ovoid form of the shells of this species.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute (< 1.7 mm), but very solid, sub-oval, milky white, shiny. Protoconch type A, with a diameter of about 200 μm , with the nucleus emerged at least in its $\frac{3}{4}$ parts. Teleoconch with almost 4 flat whorls (h > 60% H), the last one rounded at the periphery. Base slightly convex. Suture deep, canaliculated.

Axial sculpture formed by 16 robust, arched, orthocline or prosocline ribs, approximately as wide as their interspaces, which in the previous whorls reach the lower suture are abruptly interrupted at the periphery on the last whorl; on the base, only the growth lines are seen. Spiral sculpture only in the interspaces of the ribs, formed by a well-marked cord just above the suture, which does not prevent the ribs from

Figure 42. *Babella prominens* Peñas & Rolán, 2017; A-C: shells, 1.6, 1.52, 1.43 mm, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); D: apex and protoconch; E: microsculpture.

Figura 42. *Babella prominens* Peñas & Rolán, 2017; A-C: conchas, 1,6, 1,52, 1,43 mm, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MHNS); F: ápice y protoconcha; G: microescultura.

reaching the suture, and about 7-8 cordlets between this spiral cord and the upper suture; last whorl with an incipient cordlet just below the stronger cord, and four more cords on the base.

Aperture small, pyriform; columella arched, opisthocline, with a conspicuous columellar tooth. Outer lip slightly thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.6 x 0.75 mm; h = 1 mm; A = 0.5 mm.

Remarks: *Pyrgulina glycisima* Melvill, 1899, described from Karachi and cited from Japan, is different. Studying 2 syntypes (NHMUK 1899.12.1813-14), it was observed that they also have a proto-

conch of type A, but the shells are much larger, with a cyrtocoid profile; the suture is less deep, has spiral microsculpture but lacks the conspicuous cord located on the suture.

Pyrgulina claudoni Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, described from Vietnam, has a larger shell, of pyramidal conical profile; the protoconch, although also type A, has a semi-submerged nucleus, the last whorl of the teleoconch is angular at the periphery, it has numerous spiral striae between sutures and on the base only striae, not cords.

The shell which we have identified as *Babella* cf. *ovalis* (44 A-B) has a more conical

Figure 43. *Babella ovalis* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.6 mm, Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B, C: paratypes, 1.61, 1.53 mm, same locality (MNCN and MZB); D: paratype in apical view (CAP); E: protoconch; F: sculpture.

Figura 43. *Babella ovalis* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,6 mm, Jordania, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B, C: paratipos, 1,61, 1,53 mm, misma localidad (MNCN y MZB); D: paratipo en vista apical (CAP); E: protoconcha; F: escultura.

profile, a height of 1.8 mm, it is narrower, the spire is somewhat higher ($h = 55\% H$), the last whorl is broadly rounded at the periphery, the ribs are nearly orthocline,

straight, and the cord located on the periphery is more robust, but based on a single shell we are inclined to consider it as a variety of the same species.

Figure 44. A, B. *Babella* cf. *ovalis*, shell, 1.80 mm in height, Jordan, Aqaba (MNHN). C-E. *Babella micronodulosa* n. sp. C, D: holotype, 1.1 mm, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); E: protoconch. F-J. *Babella nimiaprocostae* n. sp. F, G: holotype, 1.68 mm, Sudán, Mesharifa (MNHN); H: paratype, 1.59 mm, Jordania, Aqaba (MHNS exCER); I: sculpture; J: apex and protoconch.

Figura 44. A, B. *Babella* cf. *ovalis*, concha, 1,80 mm en altura, Jordania, Aqaba (MNHN). C-E. *Babella micronodulosa* n. sp. C, D: holotipo, 1,1 mm, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); E: protoconcha. F-J. *Babella nimiaprocostae* n. sp. F, G: holotipo, 1,68 mm, Sudán, Mesharifa (MNHN); H: paratype, 1,59 mm, Jordania, Aqaba (MHNS exCER); I: escultura; J: ápice y protoconcha.

Babella micronodulosa n. sp. (Figure 44C-E)

Type material. *Holotype*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 43A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35077 (exCER). *Paratypes*: • 1 s; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/200072 (exCER) • 1 s; same data as for holotype; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (3 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The specific name is the fusion of two words: one alludes to its small size (micro) and the other the nodules which are present in the spiral cords at the crossings with the axial ribs.

Distribution: Only known in the infralittoral of the type locality, Red Sea.

Description: Shell minute (<1.5 mm), not very solid, truncate-conical, wide (H/D = 1.8), milk white, shiny. Protoconch of type C tending to B, rather high, with a diameter of about 240 μ m. Teleoconch of very short spire with 2.5 flat whorls, the last one angular at the periphery. Suture deep, canaliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by about 18 robust ribs, rounded in profile, somewhat wider than their interspaces, very prosocline, which are extended attenuated until the lower suture, once passed the spiral cord located on the suture; on the base the ribs disappear and only growth lines can be seen. Spiral sculpture formed by a thick cord located on the suture forming nodules on its junction with the ribs; the adapical area has a spiral groove close to the suture and also nodules on the upper part of the ribs.

Aperture: relatively large, sub-oval; columella curved, opisthoclinal, bordering an umbilical chink. Columellar tooth not visible. Outer lip not thickened.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 1.1 x 0.6 mm; h = 0.75 mm; A = 0.45 mm.

Remarks: At first sight, this species resembles *Egilina kotoeae* Hori & Fukuda, 1999, described from Japan, whose holotype measures 1.53 mm, although it has one whorl more, but the differences are obvious: *Egilina kotoeae* has the protoconch of type B, has less axial ribs, which are rather orthocline, suddenly interrupted before reaching the lower suture, prevented by the spiral cord above it, which is thinner and not grainy at its junction with the ribs; It also lacks an umbilical fissure and the columellar tooth is conspicuous, clearly visible.

Babella pallida Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from the circalittoral of Vanuatu, has a shell almost with the same dimensions but with one whorl more, the protoconch has a smaller diameter (200 μ m), the suprasutural cord prevents the ribs reach the suture; it lacks the groove located in the adapical area of the ribs and the columellar tooth is evident.

Babella nimiaprocostae n. sp. (Figure 44F-J)

Type material. *Holotype*: Sudan • 1 s (Fig. 44F); Mesharifa; Stn A2; MNHN-IM-2000-35078. *Paratypes*: Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 44H); Aqaba; 10 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35079 (exCER) • 1 s; Aqaba; 10 m; MNCN 15.05/200071 (exCER) • 1 s; Aqaba; 10 m; MHNS 100660 (exCER) • 1 s; Aqaba; 10 m; CAP (exCER).

Material examined (5 s): The type material.

Type locality: Sudan, Mesharifa.

Etymology: The specific name derives from the fusion of the Latin words *nimius*, *a, um* which means “too much”, *pro* which is the beginning of the word “prosocline” and *costa*, *ae* “ribs”, alluding to the very pronounced position of the axial ribs.

Distribution: Infralittoral of the Red Sea.

Description: Shell very small (< 2 mm), not very solid, conical pyramid, milk white, somewhat shiny. Proto-

conch of type C tending to B, with a diameter of about 240 μ m. Teleoconch with a moderately high spire (h = 66% H) with three flat-convex whorls, the

last one somewhat rounded at the periphery. Suture shallow, slightly canaliculate, with axial small cordlets in some parts.

Axial sculpture formed by 22-24 ribs of rounded profile, wider than their interspaces, very prosocline, thickened in their adapical area, which do not reach the suture due a disabled spiral cord located just above the suture; not prolonged on the base. Spiral sculpture formed by suprasutural cord and by numerous ridges in the interspaces of the barely visible ribs, plus a peripheral cord on the last whorl and four on the base.

Aperture sub-oval, relatively large; columella curved, opisthocline, with a late columellar tooth. Outer lip not thickened. Not umbilicated.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.68 x 0.92 mm; h = 1.02 mm; A = 0.7 mm.

Remarks: *Babella prominens* Peñas & Rolán, 2017 has a shell of similar profile and dimensions, but the protoconch is of type A, the teleoconch have fewer ribs and more robust, the cords from the base are grainy and the aperture is sub-oval and smaller.

Babella caledonica Peñas & Rolán, 2017, described from the circalittoral of New Caledonia, also has a shell with similar profile and dimensions but the protoconch, although it is also of type B, is very prominent, the last whorl of the teleoconch is very angular, has fewer ribs, about 18, more robust, has no spiral sculpture in the interspaces of the ribs and the base is smooth below the peripheral cord.

Babella maestratii n. sp. (Figure 45)

Type material. *Holotype:* Jordan • 1 s (Fig. 45A); Aqaba; 5–15 m; MNHN-IM-2000-35080 (exCER). *Paratypes:* Jordan • 3 s; same data as for holotype; MNHN-IM-2000-35081 (exCER) • 2 s; Gulf of Aqaba; MNCN 15.05/200067 • 2 s; Gulf of Aqaba; MHNS 100659 (exCBS) • 2 s; Gulf of Aqaba; MZB 60249 (exCBS) • 1 s; Gulf of Aqaba; CAP (exCBS).

Material examined (11 s): The type material.

Type locality: Jordan, Aqaba, 5–15 m.

Etymology: The new species is named after Philippe Maestrati, of MNHN, thanking him for the many shells he separated and sorted to genera for our studies.

Distribution: Known from only from the Red Sea in Aqaba.

Description: Shell very small <2.0 mm, low-solid, conical pyramidal. Milky white, shiny. Protoconch type C, with a diameter of 250 μ m. Teleoconch (H > 65% h), with three almost flat whorls, the last one angle at the periphery. Suture very deep, canaliculate.

Axial sculpture formed by 20 robust ribs, almost rectangular in profile, approximately as wide as their interspaces, almost always very prosocline, which do not reach the lower suture, abutting on a spiral cord located just above the suture, which also prevents their prolongation on the base, where only the growth lines are seen. Spiral sculpture formed by the suprasutural cord, a furrow located in the adapical zone of the ribs, a thick peripheral cord,

and about 8 more cords on the base, of which the uppermost is thicker.

Aperture relatively large, sub-oval; columella slightly arched, opisthocline, with a columellar tooth pliciform backward. Outer lip narrow. Not umbilicate.

Dimensions of the holotype: 1.65 x 0.85 mm; h = 1.1 mm; A = 0.65 mm.

Remarks: *Chrysallida ovalis* Thiele, 1930, described from Western Australia, has a very fragile, wider shell (H/D = 1.6 against 1.95 in *Babella maestratii* n. sp.), the last whorl is broadly rounded at the periphery, the sculpture is very weak, formed by at least 24 orthocline ribs and has weak spiral grooves between the ribs, in addition to those of the base.

Pyrgulina prestoni Dautzenberg & Fischer, 1907, described from Indo-

Figure 45. *Babella maestratii* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.65 mm, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B-D: paratypes, 1.7, 1.64, 1.52 mm, from the type locality; E: apex and protoconch; F: sculpture.

Figura 45. *Babella maestratii* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,65 mm, Aqaba, 5–15 m (MNHN); B-D: paratipos, 1,7, 1,64, 1,52 mm, de la localidad tipo; E: ápice y protoconcha; F: escultura.

China, has a somewhat smaller shell, with a similar profile but the whorls are flat-convex, the last one rounded at the periphery, the ribs are prolonged over the base beyond the periphery, it has spiral cordlets between the ribs and the base has not spiral sculpture.

Parthenina densesculpta Peñas & Rolán 2017, described in deep waters of the Solomon Islands and the Marquesas Archipelago, has a shell of similar size, but wider, the axial ribs extend to the base beyond the periphery, almost reaching the aperture; it lacks a subsutural groove, the base has only three or

four spiral cordlets and the columellar tooth is prominent.

Parthenina brusinai Cossmann, 1921, a typical Mediterranean species, has a larger shell with the same number of whorls and is narrower ($H/D = 2.3$ of average compared to 1.9 in *Babella maestratii* n. sp.), the last whorl is rounded or broadly rounded at the periphery, not angular, the ribs are orthocone or opisthoclinal that are prolonged on the base confused with the growth lines, on the suture has a second thinner spiral cord and lacks a subsutural furrow in the area of the ribs.

CONCLUSIONS AND COMMENTS

Number of specimens, genera and species

For the present work, we have examined around 1300 specimens and shells. Some of them were rejected due to their bad condition, being fragments or very damaged shells, from which it was impossible to get enough information. Some species were similar to other taxa previously studied from other countries, but we have limited the study only to the Red Sea material. The number of species in the genera we have studied, is as follows:

- Genus *Helodiamea*: 2 species
- Genus *Strioturbonilla*: 1 species
- Genus *Parthenina*: 12 species
- Genus *Pyrgulina*: 20 species
- Genus *Chrysallida*: 1 species
- Genus *Costabieta*: 1 species
- Genus *Miralda*: 4 species
- Genus *Oscilla*: 10 species
- Genus *Pseudoscilla*: 1 species
- Genus *Babella*: 6 species

In total, 58 species in 10 genera. As for the difficulty in collecting these shells, we must take into consideration their small size. The most usual size (30 species) was between 1 and 2 mm; between 1-2.5 mm (22 species) was next, whereas a size of more than 2.5 mm was only observed in 4 species.

Amongst the 58 species studied, 23 were previously known, while 35 were unknown and are described as new species herein. One species had a preoccupied name and is renamed.

The total of shells studied for each species was relatively low, since most of the samples were obtained by diving and collecting sediments, which were later sieved and the shells separated under a stereomicroscope. Dredgings from ships, which would have increased the number of available species and shells, were not available.

The largest amount of shells was obtained for *Pyrgulina erecta* (176 shells), followed by *P. linomicalii* n. sp. and *P. maiae*, with 92 and 83 shells respectively. Four species only were represented by 30 to 50 shells: *Helodiamea prima* n. sp. with

42 shells, *Pyrgulina craticulata*, with 31, *Costabieta fabrei* with 46, and *Oscilla virginiae* n. sp. with 45. Only 12 species had a number of shells from 11 to 30: *Parthenina sudanensis* n. sp., *Parthenina perforata* n. sp., *Pyrgulina microtuber* n. sp., *Pyrgulina minusgranum* n. sp., *Pyrgulina condita* n. sp., *Pyrgulina lacrima* n. sp., *Miralda protogalea*, *Oscilla beccarii*, *O. composita*, *O. belardi*, *O. cylindrica*, *O. multistriata* n. sp.

Finally, some other species were only collected in a very short number: *Pyrgulina prosoribs* n. sp. and *Chrysallida yamaniaensis* n. sp. are only known for the holotype. *Pyrgulina carmeloi* n. sp. with only 2 shells. *Parthenina elegantiae* n. sp., *Pyrgulina isae* n. sp., *Pyrgulina scabra* n. sp., and *Babella micronodulosa* n. sp. were described with only 3 shells each. The rest with a number between 4 and 10.

Bathymetric distribution

It is always difficult to define the depth at which the species lived, in samples where much of the material was collected in sediments. Nevertheless, when studying large amounts of material and taking into account the findings of many species, some conclusions can be reached. Anyway, in the present work we have not employing deep dredgings, also no collecting in the intertidal, due that most of the collectors were expert in diving and this seemed to be a better collecting method. Also, from some material found by other persons, we lacked information regarding the depth at which the species were collected.

From the total of the species studied, only in two cases we have information that they were collected at 2 m deep. The other species were collected between 10 and 30 m.

Geographic distribution and endemism

The study area not being very small (the Red Sea) and the samples made in very limited places, it is clear that it is very difficult to show a complete and accurate geographic distribution of the species included in this work. Anyway,

we have split the Red Sea into the countries bordering its coast: Jordan, Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Eritrea, Sudan and Yemen. It is true that most of the collecting was done in Jordan and Egypt, hence most of the material comes from there. So, we only can provide some information, which will be completed in future expeditions.

From Jordan, 45 species were collected. From the Egypt coast we have material of 33 species. These two countries being the most intensely sampled, it must be considered normal that Jordan is the type locality of 23 of the new species here described, while Egypt is the type locality of 5 new species, Eritrea is only the type locality of 2 new species, and Sudan the type locality of 3 new species. Curiously, for the previously known species, Eritrea was the type locality of 8 of them, studied in the present work, reflecting that in the past this country was more thoroughly sampled than recently. Finally, from Arabia Saudi we have material of 5 species and from Yemen, only one species.

This is of course due to the fact that in some areas our sampling was very scarce or null.

It is possible that many studied species be endemic of the Red Sea, but at present this is impossible to be evaluated because for most of them the number of shells collected was very low and also the nearby coasts of the Indian Ocean were hardly sampled.

Some of the species in the present study were known from other countries, some being very remote like Borneo, Japan, Vanuatu, Hawaii, South Africa, etc.

Species described in other works but not collected by the authors

Pyrgulina ventricosa Hornung & Mermod, 1925. A syntype of this was examined and photographed, being rather similar to *P. maiae*.

Cingulina (Odetta) nodulosa Hornung & Mermod, 1924. Two examined and photographed (5645-5665 y 5718-5740) are in very bad condition; anyway, we think that this species is different from the material here described.

Pyrgulina? problematica Hornung & Mermod, 1924. Two syntypes were examined and photographed, one of them was in bad condition (5870.5890) and it is not coincident with the other one (5956-5983), neither with the description of the species. The second one lacks the apex and we think that it is a *Turbonilla*.

Pyrgulina edgarii Melvill, 1896, also recorded by HORNUNG & MERMOD, 1925. The type material was examined and photographed, five syntypes (NHMUK 1896.10.13.1-5); it is a species of the group of *P. maiae*, which we have not found in our material.

Pyrgulina crystallopecta Melvill, 1910, also recorded by HORNUNG & MERMOD, 1924. We have examined and photographed the holotype of this species (NHMUK 1912.8.16.41) and reached the conclusion that it is a species of the tribe Turbonillini. We have found some shells of this species in the Red Sea, which will be studied in a future article.

Odostomia (Pyrgulina) thelxinoa Melvill, 1906, also recorded by HORNUNG & MERMOD, 1924. We have examined the three syntypes (NHMUK 1906.10.23.36-37) and we think that they belong to the tribe Turbonillini.

Odostomia (Miralda) ima Melvill, 1906, recorded by HORNUNG & MERMOD, 1925. We have examined and photographed the type material (NHMUK 1906.10.23.78-81) and we have not found this species in the Red Sea.

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